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Designing apprenticeships

A guidance note for practitioners
and policy-makers in Africa

Markus Maurer
Rubain Bankole
Tsinu Amdeselassie Worku
Samuel Derrer
Michael Morlok
Christine Hofmann

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Foreword

Across the African continent, the transition of young people into decent work remains one of the most pressing development challenges—and one of the greatest opportunities. With a rapidly growing and youthful population, countries are placing increasing emphasis on skills development systems that are inclusive, relevant and responsive to labour market realities. In this context, apprenticeships—both in the formal and the informal economy—play a central role. They provide pathways into work for millions of young people, while supporting enterprises in accessing the skills they need to grow and remain competitive.

This Guidance Note on designing apprenticeships responds to this priority. It aims to support policy-makers, practitioners and social partners in strengthening apprenticeship systems in ways that are grounded in local realities and aligned with broader development objectives. It reflects the recognition that effective apprenticeship systems cannot be built from scratch but must evolve from existing practices—often deeply rooted in national and local economies—through gradual, context-sensitive improvements.

The Guidance Note builds on ILO’s Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208), which provides a comprehensive normative framework for strengthening apprenticeship systems. It translates key principles of the Recommendation into practical design considerations, offering concrete guidance on how to improve the quality, inclusiveness and relevance of apprenticeships across diverse African contexts. In doing so, it builds on ILO’s global [Guide for Policymakers - Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 \(No. 208\) | International Labour Organization](#), provides an update to the 2012 Resource guide on upgrading informal apprenticeships in Africa, and reflects the growing body of experience and evidence generated over the past decade on apprenticeships on the Continent.

This publication contributes to broader regional and continental efforts to advance skills development embedded within Africa’s productive sectors. It is fully consistent with the African Union’s Continental Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Strategy and supports the objectives of the ILO–African Union Youth Employment in Africa (YES Africa) strategy. By strengthening apprenticeship systems, countries can expand access to skills, promote transitions to formality, and improve employment outcomes for young women and men.

The Guidance Note draws on extensive collaboration and research. It benefits from the insights of practitioners, policy-makers and experts across multiple countries, as well as from the dedicated work of the author team, whose expertise and commitment made this publication possible. We are also grateful for the valuable inputs of ILO colleagues, including Patrick Daru, Karim Toumi and Albert Okal, and for the contributions of external reviewers, which helped strengthen the analysis and ensure its relevance. We would also like to recognize the ILO’s Africa Skills Hub as the ILO’s continental knowledge platform for skills development. This Guidance Note adds to the growing portfolio of knowledge products developed under the Hub, aimed at supporting countries in addressing skills and employment challenges across the continent.

We hope that this Guidance Note will serve as a practical resource and a source of inspiration for all those engaged in designing and strengthening apprenticeship systems across Africa. By working together—governments, employers’ and workers’ organizations, training institutions and development partners—we can ensure that apprenticeships deliver on their promise: equipping young people with relevant skills, supporting enterprises, and contributing to sustainable development and social justice.

Fanfan Rwanyindo Kayirangwa
Regional Director | ILO Regional Office for Africa

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List of abbreviations

BAA	Bureau d'Appui aux Artisans (Benin)
CAP	Certificat d'Aptitude Professionnelle (Benin, Côte d'Ivoire)
CQM	Certificat de Qualification aux Métiers (Benin, Côte d'Ivoire)
CQP	Certificat de Qualification Professionnelle (Benin, Côte d'Ivoire)
DGEFTP	Direction Générale de l'Enseignement et de la Formation Techniques et Professionnels (Benin)
EFAT	Examen de Fin d'Apprentissage (Benin)
FODEFCA	Fonds de Développement de la Formation Professionnelle Continue et de l'Apprentissage (Benin)
ILO	International Labour Organization
INIFRCF	Institut National de l'Ingénierie de Formation et de Renforcement des Capacités des Formateurs (Benin)
MFPA	Ministère de la Formation professionnelle, de l'Apprentissage et de l'Artisanat (Senegal)
NQF	National qualifications framework
OHS	Occupational health and safety
RPL	Recognition of prior learning
ToT	Training of trainers
VAE	Validation des acquis de l'expérience
VETA	Vocational Education and Training Authority (Tanzania)
VET	Vocational education and training
WAEMU	West African Economic and Monetary Union (West Africa)
YIEDIE	Youth Inclusive Entrepreneurial Development Initiative for Employment (Ghana)

1. Introduction

Given the significant challenge young people in Africa face in gaining access to the labour market, there is strong political interest in measures that can improve their transition into employment. Much of this attention is directed towards interventions in vocational skills development. At the same time, there is growing recognition that strengthening formal vocational education and training (VET), as it currently exists in many countries of the region, is not enough. In fact, such systems are often insufficiently aligned with labour market needs, and they tend to exclude large numbers of young people who do not possess the level of general schooling required for entry. For many policy-makers in Africa, it therefore appears more promising to focus on strengthening apprenticeship systems, which in many cases are only loosely coupled to formal VET systems.

Apprenticeships offer important advantages: they are very common all over the continent, particularly in craft occupations and selected service sectors in rural areas, where the workplace serves not only as a site of production but also as a space in which skills, habits and professional values are acquired through direct participation and observation. In many African contexts, this form of learning has evolved within community-based and small-enterprise settings shaped by social relations, trust and local norms. At the same time, traditional apprenticeships face considerable challenges, including a high degree of dependency on master craftspersons and limited opportunities for educational mobility. As a result, apprenticeships have lost some of their attractiveness for young people in Africa.

In this context, the International Labour Organization's Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208) is of particular relevance. It highlights key dimensions of quality apprenticeships and can support the gradual formalisation of such systems, thereby contributing to enhancing their appeal and improving opportunities for young people across the continent.

1.1 Rationale and objectives of the Guidance Note

Yet, implementing the Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208), referred to as R208 in this guidance note, is neither straightforward nor linear. It requires building on existing structures, working closely with key stakeholders and adapting promising models to sector- and country-specific realities. This inevitably raises questions of how to translate principles into workable arrangements on the ground. The task is therefore not to apply a ready-made blueprint, but to realise the underlying idea of quality apprenticeships in ways that fit local economic, social and cultural conditions – a process that typically advances step by step and needs to be grounded in social dialogue.

At the same time, those who wish to engage in this work need to be aware of the range of options available to them at different levels of the system. These design options form the core of this Guidance Note. They are, in this report, not presented as a toolbox to be applied uniformly across countries, but rather as a broad overview of the possibilities that exist within apprenticeship and work-based learning systems. The Guidance Note therefore offers practical orientation for stakeholders involved in the design, delivery and support of apprenticeships in Africa. It addresses policy-makers who shape national-level strategies and regulations, funding arrangements and coordination structures, as well as practitioners, including representatives of training institutions, employers' and workers' organisations, and intermediary bodies.

Given the central importance of apprenticeships across much of Africa, the Note adopts a deliberately inclusive understanding of the concept. It recognises the coexistence of formal and informal apprenticeship systems, both of which make substantial contributions to skills development and employment. In many African economies, informal apprenticeships remain the predominant form of training, providing access to work for millions of young people, while formal schemes – though smaller in scale – offer structured learning pathways and mechanisms for recognition that can inform or complement informal systems.

The primary focus of the Guidance Note is therefore on design aspects: how apprenticeship systems are planned, developed and supported in practice. While legal or contractual dimensions such as minimum age requirements, training duration or payment arrangements form an important part of national apprenticeship frameworks, they are not examined in a systematic manner here. Rather, such regulatory elements appear only as contextual variables where they illuminate implementation challenges or opportunities.

1.2 Key sources of the Guidance Note

This Guidance Note builds on a substantial body of existing research and policy work on apprenticeships and work-based learning in Africa, including earlier ILO reports, toolkits and analytical studies. In particular, it draws on insights from the ILO Guide for Policymakers - Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208), global and regional reviews of skills development, and research on the upgrading of apprenticeships in the informal economy in African and other low- and middle-income country contexts. It provides updates to the ILO's Resource guide for Africa on upgrading informal apprenticeship (2012) in light of R208. Yet, to enhance readability, the Guidance Note does not include in-text references. Relevant background literature is instead listed in the section "Background literature".

Furthermore, the preparation of this Guidance Note encompassed additional research focusing on six specific countries to provide updated, practice-oriented evidence. The country sample is represented by Benin, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Senegal, Tanzania and Uganda, which were selected by the ILO based on a sample of countries with ongoing apprenticeship reforms, covering different geographic regions. This research included:

- ▶ **document review** of relevant materials such as training plans, curricula, assessment tools and regulatory texts;
- ▶ **interviews with experts and practitioners** involved in apprenticeship delivery, coordination and policy; and
- ▶ **analysis of how apprenticeship systems operate** in both formal and informal sectors.

Together, these case studies and sources form the empirical and conceptual foundation of this Guidance Note, along with the Quality Apprenticeship Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208). They illustrate the diversity of African apprenticeship systems – understood not only as systems governed by formal institutions and legal frameworks, but also by social norms and traditions – and provide the grounding for the principles and key messages that follow.

1.3 Structure of the Guidance Note

This Guidance Note is structured to guide readers from foundations to practical implementation steps, most relevant in African countries. Following the introduction, Chapter 2 outlines design foundations for apprenticeship training. Chapter 3 presents nine key dimensions – grouped into four clusters. Chapters 4–6 translate these design choices into practical tools for developing occupational content, strengthening workplace learning and defining off-the-job components. Chapter 7 discusses assessment and recognition mechanisms, including recognition of prior learning (RPL), and Chapter 8 concludes.

Throughout the report, country examples from Africa presented in dedicated boxes illustrate how these elements have been applied in practice (see also section 1.4 below).

In addition to these boxes featuring country examples, two further types of boxes are used, which are briefly introduced here.

First, there are boxes highlighting key messages on apprenticeship programmes. These refer directly to the ILO Apprenticeship Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208) and are marked in orange.

Second, there are boxes providing specific guidance on the design of apprenticeship programmes, drawing attention to aspects that require particular consideration – in some cases also highlighting potential trade-offs. These boxes are marked in green.

1.4 About the use of good practices in this Guidance Note

Throughout this Guidance Note, good practices are used to illustrate key concepts and show how different elements of apprenticeship systems have been developed in practice. They also demonstrate that, in many parts of Africa, considerable progress has been made in recent years in strengthening both formal and informal apprenticeship pathways.

The selected examples are intended to be inspiring and instructive. They reflect on the work undertaken by governments, training institutions, social partners and development organisations, and they show that well-designed initiatives can provide young people with meaningful pathways into employment.

At the same time, two important qualifications must be kept in mind:

- ▶ The **examples presented** are not based on impact evaluations or systematic effectiveness studies. No independent assessments or measurements of outcomes were conducted in the context of this study.
- ▶ Many **initiatives highlighted** in this Note have a pilot or project-based character and rely on substantial support from international partners. Their long-term sustainability remains an open question, particularly where special funding arrangements or external incentives have been required to achieve results.

Despite these limitations, the examples demonstrate that progress is possible even under challenging conditions, and that pragmatic, context-sensitive approaches can strengthen apprenticeships in ways that benefit both learners and enterprises. They are shared here not as definitive models, but as sources of inspiration for adaptation and further development.

2. Foundations of apprenticeship design most relevant for Africa

Building on R208 and the contextual realities outlined in the introduction, this section outlines key foundations for shaping and strengthening apprenticeship training across Africa. The term “design” is used broadly: in many contexts, it refers not to constructing systems from scratch but to supporting, upgrading and connecting existing forms of apprenticeship – formal or informal – so that they can function more effectively and inclusively.

Formal apprenticeship schemes can often be improved through clearer frameworks, stronger coordination and better support for enterprises and learners. Informal apprenticeships, by contrast, usually operate outside formal structures and depend on local norms and relationships. They are not designed in a formal sense, but they can be strengthened through pragmatic measures such as mentoring support, learning materials, protection from occupational safety and health risks or recognition of prior learning (RPL).

The following foundations therefore provide orientation for initiatives that seek to enhance, link or adapt apprenticeship practices to the institutional, social and economic conditions in which they already exist with a view to enhance their effectiveness and quality. The aim is not to standardise, but to enable gradual improvement in ways that make sense for the people, enterprises and communities involved.

Foundation 1: Shared responsibility and dialogue within context

The effectiveness of apprenticeship training depends on cooperation among multiple stakeholders who recognise a shared responsibility for programme outcomes. A central element is tripartite collaboration between government authorities, employers' and workers' organizations. The latter can also act as intermediary organisations in the context of apprenticeships. However, their capacity and resources vary greatly across African contexts.

In many parts of the informal economy, artisans coordinate their activities through informal arrangements that fall short of functioning as fully established associations. In some countries, crafts associations affiliate with national employers' organizations, in others, with workers' organizations. Both are important partners for national-level apprenticeship policies, but their engagement typically focuses on the formal sector. Moreover, compared to crafts or trade associations and national or sectoral employers' organizations, workers' organizations often play only a marginal role in shaping occupational profiles or content standards, even though they can play a very critical role in apprenticeships.

In addition to employers' and workers' organizations, identifying the stakeholders who are truly influential in a given context is therefore essential – and they must be engaged carefully and meaningfully. This includes, in some countries, also parents' associations, which can play a significant role in apprenticeship systems in the informal economy and should be involved accordingly, as is the case in Benin.

Senegal

Shared responsibility through negotiated arrangements in informal apprenticeships

In Senegal, efforts to strengthen apprenticeships in the informal sector rely less on creating new qualifications and more on negotiated coordination among existing stakeholders. The responsible ministry (the Ministère de la Formation professionnelle, de l'Apprentissage et de l'Artisanat MFPAA) works with chambers of crafts (Chambres de Métiers), sectoral artisans' organisations and, in some cases, parents' representatives to agree on basic rules for apprenticeship conditions, assessment procedures and end-of-training examinations. While these arrangements do not constitute a fully formalised apprenticeship system, they create shared expectations regarding training duration, roles and responsibilities. Mixed examination juries – typically composed of experienced artisans, representatives of craft organisations and MFPAA officials – illustrate this shared responsibility in practice. The Senegalese experience shows that dialogue-based governance, even without new formal credentials, can improve transparency and trust while remaining compatible with the realities of informal workshops.

Foundation 2: Relevance to local economies and livelihoods

Efforts to strengthen apprenticeships may pursue social or educational policy goals (see Section 3.6), yet the defining feature of apprenticeships remains their strong reliance on the world of work. For this reason, a deep understanding of local economic realities is essential. Across much of Africa, apprenticeships take place in small enterprises or informal workshops that serve local markets, where technologies, inputs and demand conditions are highly context specific.

For many artisans, the gradual formalisation of apprenticeships can be economically attractive for different reasons, but in particular because it can secure better access to labour – an important incentive particularly in contexts characterised by skills shortages. However, some policy objectives associated with apprenticeship reforms – such as increasing the mobility of workers across regions or trades – may be less aligned with the interests of these enterprises.

Designing for relevance therefore requires starting from the actual organisation of work and the competences needed for day-to-day production, rather than importing occupational classifications or training models developed elsewhere. Employers, master craftspersons and trade associations are best positioned to indicate which skills matter locally and how they are most effectively learned, so that enhanced apprenticeships ultimately lead to a recognized qualification.

Ghana

Apprenticeships aligned with skills needs in the formal construction sector

In Ghana, engagement in apprenticeship reforms within the construction sector is driven by concrete economic concerns. Contractors in the formal construction industry face persistent skills shortages, growing quality requirements and increasing pressure from clients to meet technical standards, timelines and safety norms. Against this backdrop, industry bodies such as the Association of Building and Civil Engineering Contractors of Ghana have supported apprenticeship initiatives by standardizing learning content that strengthen practical skills formation in trades relevant to modern construction sites. Their interest lies in improving workmanship, reducing costly errors and ensuring a more reliable pipeline of skilled workers for the sector. This example illustrates how apprenticeships gain traction when they respond directly to sector-specific production needs and quality expectations, particularly in parts of the economy where formal enterprises depend on skilled labour to remain competitive.

Foundation 3: Creating conditions for learning at the workplace

Work-based training achieves its potential when the workplace becomes a genuine learning space rather than simply a site of labour. Even small and informal enterprises can strengthen learning by organising simple but structured training arrangements in a safe and healthy working environment: clear expectations of tasks, gradual progression in difficulty, regular feedback and opportunities for observation.

Where resources allow, basic learning tools such as logbooks or task lists can help structure instruction and track progress. In the absence of formal trainer preparation, peer learning and short mentoring sessions can be used to enhance guidance. The focus is on achievable improvements – small changes that make learning more intentional and transparent for both in-house trainer or master craftsperson and apprentice.

Senegal

Learning through social organisation in informal workshops

In Senegal’s traditional workshops, as in the informal sector in most other African countries, master craftspersons intentionally structure progression from observation to independent work, often supported by strong social bonds and moral contracts. These embedded pedagogical routines transform even small, resource-poor workshops into real learning environments. The practice highlights how effective learning can emerge from social discipline and gradual responsibility, not from formal pedagogy alone.

Foundation 4: Flexibility and progressive improvement

Given the diversity of African apprenticeship systems, design must prioritise flexibility and allow for progressive improvement over time. Systems that are too prescriptive risk excluding the very enterprises and learners that sustain apprenticeship in practice.

Flexible design means accommodating differences in enterprise capacity, literacy levels, needs of learners, duration and entry requirements. Informal apprenticeships can be strengthened through light-touch agreements based on adequate social dialogue, short complementary training, and recognition of prior learning opportunities for trainers that validate existing competences, or for apprentices to access, take short-cuts, or be certified at the end of apprenticeship if a recognition of prior learning system is used for end of apprenticeship exams.

Monitoring of training should emphasise learning outcomes and employability rather than strict adherence to training procedures. By encouraging experimentation, feedback and peer exchange, systems can evolve incrementally – becoming more coherent and credible without losing their accessibility or responsiveness.

Benin

Incremental development of the CQM exam

The CQM examination in Benin has evolved directly from informal assessment practices used by artisans to evaluate the end of an apprenticeship. Building on this tradition, the local NGO Bureau d'Appui aux Artisans (BAA) helped structure the former Examen de Fin d'Apprentissage (EFAT) into a more coherent, competence-based assessment. The local administration supported this initiative by legitimizing the examination process and authenticating the informal diplomas issued to apprentices by master craftspeople and their associations. To strengthen the status of informal sector training, the government later accredited the CQM exam through the Apprenticeship Act 117/2005, turning a locally rooted practice into a nationally recognised certification.

This gradual, bottom-up development has been essential for system ownership. Artisans remain closely involved in defining tasks and practical tests, ensuring that the exam reflects real workshop practice. Interviews indicate that the CQM continues to attract strong participation precisely because entry barriers are low and the qualification matches informal sector realities. The CQM thus illustrates how certification can be expanded incrementally – without imposing formal system requirements that would risk excluding the majority of informal apprentices.

3. Defining the cornerstones of apprenticeship programmes

Before designing or reforming apprenticeship programmes, stakeholders require clarity about the fundamental design choices that determine how an apprenticeship functions in practice. In addition to the main parts of R208 that define the regulatory framework, the protection of apprentices, the agreement, equality and diversity, and apprenticeship promotion, this guidance note provides an additional analytical lens and further details on contextual factors of particular relevance to African countries. These choices shape not only the learning experience of apprentices, but also the feasibility, sustainability and labour market relevance of the programme.

This chapter presents nine key dimensions along which such design choices need to be made. For clarity, these dimensions are grouped into four clusters, reflecting the different layers of an apprenticeship system. Taken together, these dimensions structure the “cornerstones” of any apprenticeship programme. The chapter concludes by explaining why these decisions matter for implementation and how they are inseparable from the policy objectives that apprenticeship reforms seek to achieve. Crucially, these objectives ought to be shared – or at least broadly supported – by the key stakeholders involved if apprenticeships are to take root and deliver meaningful outcomes.

Dimensions of Apprenticeship Programmes

3.1 The economic sector dimension

Efforts to strengthen vocational skills development - including apprenticeships - inevitably require strategic decisions about which economic sectors to prioritise. These choices are rarely neutral: they are strongly shaped by national development agendas and political objectives (see Section 3.6), which often identify specific sectors as drivers of growth, employment or regional development.

Across West and Central African countries, the most prominent apprenticeship reforms have taken place in the crafts sector¹. This is unsurprising: crafts play a central role in local economies in both urban and rural areas, and reform initiatives can build on long-standing apprenticeship traditions. Strengthening training in these trades in many cases aligns well with both economic and social policy goals, as it supports sectors with large employment potential.

At the same time, governments and development partners have sought to extend apprenticeships into sectors where such traditions are weak or largely absent. Agriculture is a prominent example, yet developing apprenticeship models for primary agricultural production has proven difficult (see box below). Similar efforts - though mostly at higher qualification levels - have also emerged in more urban and service-oriented sectors such as banking or ICT, as illustrated by the bachelor-level apprenticeship programmes in Tanzania (see box in Section 3.4), or also in mining.

Overall, sector selection shapes not only the feasibility of apprenticeship implementation but also the types of learning environments available, the forms of training structure that are realistic, and the policy instruments required to make apprenticeships meaningful and attractive.

Uganda

Developing apprenticeships in agriculture

Efforts to introduce apprenticeships in agriculture have repeatedly faced structural constraints in many countries in the region: production is seasonal, workplaces are dispersed, and much of the labour is embedded in household-based farming. Moreover, apprenticeship traditions in farming itself are often lacking, as knowledge and skills are typically transmitted within families across generations. As a result, initiatives to strengthen apprenticeships have focused not on core farming activities, but on specialised occupations within the agricultural sector. Uganda, for example, currently designs apprenticeship pathways for agricultural machinists and artificial insemination technicians. These programmes combine substantial on-the-job learning with structured off-the-job modules and lead to recognised qualifications, illustrating how apprenticeships can be developed in sectors without strong training traditions by targeting specialised, employment-relevant roles.

¹ While statistically not an economic sector, some countries consider the crafts sector as a separate economic sector. Others include it under creative and cultural industries, or consider it cross-cutting throughout light manufacturing, tourism industries, retail trade, mining and construction.

3.2 Dimensions that underlie the formalisation of apprenticeships

Often in Africa – as well as elsewhere – a distinction is made between informal and formal apprenticeships. However, this distinction is too simplistic. R208 recommends measures to facilitate the transition from the informal to the formal economy, by strengthening the capacity of economic units and their associations through business and financial services, better training methods and skills of master craftspersons, off-the job learning, recognition of prior learning and bridging courses. When considering formalisation, two separate dimensions need to be distinguished.

A) Relationship to labour law

A first defining dimension is how the apprenticeship stands in relation to labour legislation, or other relevant legal frameworks such as laws on education, the crafts sector, industry, collective agreements, or secondary legislation such as decrees under relevant Ministries.

1. Apprenticeship status according to laws and regulations

In some countries, apprenticeships are regulated primarily as a specific employment relationship, in others, apprentices are considered learners or students not fully covered by labour law provisions. R208 specifies rights to protection of apprentices, and lists provisions that should be included in apprenticeship agreements, including duration, remuneration or other financial compensation, hours of work, social security, and so forth.

2. Apprenticeships in the informal economy

Common in the informal economy, apprenticeship agreements rely largely on social contracts between enterprises (or master craftspersons) and apprentices (or their parents). They typically do not fully apply all provisions and protections that national laws and regulations foresee, such as remuneration, regulated hours of work, occupational safety and health, or social security. In principle, national laws and regulations also apply to these apprenticeships; in practice, however, provisions related to apprenticeship training are less systematically enforced, monitored or sanctioned in informal settings.

B) Degree of formalisation in the training and assessment process

The second central dimension concerns the presence or absence of structured training content and assessment procedures.

1. Non-formalised apprenticeships

These rely mainly on workplace learning without defined training content or assessment procedures.

2. Formalised training pathways

These include defined occupational profiles and curricula and sometimes integrate off-the-job training. They normally lead to recognised qualifications.

These dimensions in reality

In practice, these two dimensions do not always align neatly. Many apprenticeships that are formally anchored in laws and regulations still lack structured training elements and do not lead to recognised qualifications. Conversely, some apprenticeships in the informal economy have begun to incorporate more structured learning components, even though they remain outside the full scope of laws and regulations. Moreover, certain regulatory provisions may be well intentioned, yet when these requirements are set too high, they may deter young people or companies from entering apprenticeships in the first place. According to ILO's Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No.138) apprentices should have a minimum of 14 years in programmes approved by the competent authority, after consultation with the organisations of employers and workers concerned.

Quality apprenticeships

ILO's R208 encourages a gradual move toward more formal apprenticeship arrangements, both in how training is organised and how apprentices are engaged – based on social dialogue. In many African economies, apprenticeships in the informal economy are still the most common, so the key issue is often less about legal classification and more about whether the apprenticeship provides some structured training that helps apprentices learn and build skills. R208 also highlights the importance of rights and protection: all apprentices should in principle be protected under the law. In practice, this is not always the case – even in the formal economy – but protection can be strengthened through standard apprenticeship agreements that clarify expectations for both apprentices and trainers, and are signed by a third party; and by other measures such as increased awareness, effective complaints and dispute resolution mechanism, support services etc.

Benin and Côte d'Ivoire

Formalised apprenticeships in the informal sector

Benin and Côte d'Ivoire have gradually worked to formalise informal apprenticeships. Young people can now complete informal apprenticeships that lead to the Certificat de Qualification aux Métiers (CQM) and, at a more advanced level, the Certification de Qualification Professionnelle (CQP), qualifications specifically tailored to the realities of apprenticeships in the informal sector. Although these apprenticeships continue to operate outside formal labour legislation, they are increasingly aligned with provisions inspired by the WAEMU apprenticeship code, which recommends, among other elements, a minimum entry age of 15. This requirement is challenging to implement in both countries' informal economies, where early entry into apprenticeships is still widespread.

This model illustrates how informal apprenticeships can acquire structure, recognition and clearer learning expectations while not (yet) fully applying apprenticeship laws and regulations. Yet the two countries differ in several aspects of implementation – differences that will be examined in later sections of this report (see, for example, Section 5.4.2).

3.3 Dimensions of the apprenticeship relationship

Beyond these two core dimensions, there are also important dimensions that relate to the organisation of the apprenticeship relationship.

A) Selection of apprentices

- ▶ Direct selection by workshops or enterprises. This is the predominant option in most apprenticeships in the informal economy and remains common even in many formal apprenticeship schemes. Selection is usually based on the artisans' social networks, which also implies that master artisans with a good reputation in their field are recommended by parents for training.
- ▶ Selection or matching by public institutions or programmes, often when targeting specific groups.

B) Financing

Financing arrangements in apprenticeships vary widely and reflect underlying power relations, labour-market conditions and policy priorities. Rather than fitting into a single model, they span a continuum of payment flows between apprentices, enterprises and families.

▶ Apprentices receive compensation

In many apprenticeship contexts, apprentices obtain some form of income or allowance through enterprise-paid stipends or wages. Such allowances are often modest and may be paid weekly or, in some cases, even daily. These arrangements enhance the attractiveness and inclusiveness of apprenticeships, but they are typically viable only where enterprises benefit from apprentices' productivity or face skills shortages. R208 calls for remuneration or other financial compensation, hence considering in-kind payments as insufficient.

▶ Training fees paid by families

In several West African contexts, families contribute financially to secure a training place with a master craftsman. While artisans often regard these fees as justified compensation for training efforts, this model is problematic from a social and educational policy perspective, as it systematically disadvantages youth from low-income households.

▶ No direct payment, compensation through labour

In other settings, apprentices neither receive allowances nor pay fees. Instead, training costs are implicitly offset through apprentices' labour contributions over extended periods, sometimes combined with informal agreements to remain in the enterprise after training.

To promote more inclusive and sustainable apprenticeships, public authorities and development partners often cover some of the costs – for example through subsidies, stipends or other financial mechanisms paid out of national budgets or training funds financed by levies. Such mechanisms can support compensation arrangements, but their long-term viability depends on stable domestic financing rather than project-based support.

C) Contractual aspects

Apprenticeships are always based on some form of agreement between apprentices and enterprises (or master craftspersons and artisans respectively). Depending on the context, this may take the form of:

- ▶ **unwritten arrangements** grounded in locally recognised norms and practices,
- ▶ **informal** but written agreements without reference to a formal legal framework, or
- ▶ **written contracts** under formal legal provisions – which is recommended in R208.

Reliability of apprenticeship agreements is critical for their economic viability: Since returns for enterprises typically materialize only toward the end of the training period, it is important that apprentices commit to stay.

In country examples covered in this guidance note, informal but written agreements have proven to be important for the formalisation of apprenticeships. They can form the basis for admission to a trade test (in Benin, for example, for the exams leading to the CQM or CQP).

Furthermore, where apprenticeships take place according to laws and regulations within formal sector enterprises, apprenticeship agreements are often cosigned by a third party authorized by the public authority responsible for regulating apprenticeships – as stipulated in R208.

These dimensions in reality

In many parts of Africa, the practical reality along these dimensions is straightforward: apprentices are most often selected directly by workshops or enterprises, and many apprenticeships – especially in the informal economy – operate without financial compensation for learners. This reduces costs for enterprises but makes apprenticeships far less attractive for many young people, who therefore try to enter the labour market directly as casual workers, thus limiting career progression, or look for other education and training options – often with limited chances of success.

Quality apprenticeships

Moving gradually towards the vision embodied in the Quality Apprenticeships approach – particularly regarding apprentice remuneration and the formalisation of the training relationship – requires considerable sensitivity, realism and patience from all stakeholders involved. Progress is possible, but typically emerges step by step according to contexts. Advances are most feasible in sectors facing labour shortages, where enterprises have stronger incentives to invest in attracting and retaining apprentices.

Uganda

Financing apprenticeships for refugee youth in the hospitality sector

In Uganda’s hospitality apprenticeship programmes, apprentices are paid a modest stipend to support essential daily expenses such as transport and basic subsistence. At present, these stipends are largely financed by development partners ILO and Enabel. However, UHOA is deliberately transitioning toward a more sustainable model in which participating enterprises progressively assume responsibility for paying apprentices. This approach is already being implemented in a number of participating hotels. The stipend remains modest but meaningful, particularly for apprentices from vulnerable backgrounds, including refugees, who often lack family or social safety nets. By offsetting basic participation costs without distorting incentives for both businesses and apprentices to join, the model demonstrates how shared responsibility between development partners and enterprises can expand access, strengthen employer ownership, and embed apprenticeships more firmly within the operational realities of the hospitality sector.

Tanzania

Flexibilising apprenticeship arrangements in the absence of formal contracts

Contractual agreements can enhance predictability and trust among all parties involved in apprenticeships. For many years, Tanzania's National College of Tourism used formal apprenticeship contracts with hotels and learners. Following the post-COVID crisis in the hospitality sector, these contracts were suspended, and cooperation has since continued on a more flexible basis. While these informal arrangements offer greater flexibility for enterprises, they are less favourable from the perspective of learners and policy-makers. Nevertheless, they have enabled apprenticeship training to continue pragmatically under challenging economic conditions.

3.4 Education and training systems dimensions

Apprenticeships are not only shaped by their contractual and organisational arrangements, but also by the way they are positioned within national education and training systems.

A) Type and level of qualification

A particularly decisive dimension concerns the type and level of qualification to which an apprenticeship leads.

▶ No access to qualification

Typical in informal systems, where skills are recognised mainly through local reputation and employer perception. Accordingly, most apprentices in African countries do not receive a certificate at the end of their training.

▶ Access to qualification, often placed at a specific level of a qualifications system or framework. Depending on the system, this may include:

- **Formal qualifications** embedded in the education system and offering progression opportunities. Typically, vocational programmes that are integrated into the education system – especially where they open pathways to further training – lead to such formal qualifications.
- **Non-formal qualifications** with limited or no access to further education. Depending on the context, such qualifications are either deliberately integrated into the qualifications system or framework or intentionally kept outside of it.

Quality apprenticeships typically culminate in a recognised credential, and this has direct implications for programme design: the duration of training usually needs to be defined, and some form of off-the-job instruction becomes necessary to cover theoretical and foundational components.

In addition, two further aspects gain importance when apprenticeships are linked to recognised qualifications:

1. **Entry requirements.** What level of prior education or foundational skills is needed to begin the apprenticeship? How do these requirements vary across occupations?
2. **Progression opportunities.** What further education or professional pathways does the qualification open up?

While these are technical questions, they carry strategic implications: they influence who can access formalised apprenticeships and how such programmes are valued by society and the labour market.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Balancing the objectives of permeability and of labour market relevance

Evidence from practice shows that apprenticeships offering clear progression routes attract broader participation and social recognition. However, if progression becomes the dominant motivation, the risk arises that apprenticeships lose their work orientation and serve primarily as stepping stones to higher levels in the education and training system.

Hence, apprenticeship design must find a balance between upward permeability and labour market relevance. The most promising programmes are those where the qualification is *required* or *rewarded* by employers – as illustrated by the case of welders in Tanzania, where firms systematically recruit only those holding recognised apprenticeship certificates. This demonstrates how structured qualifications can achieve both social legitimacy and economic utility.

Benin and Côte d'Ivoire

Informal sector qualifications CQM and CQP

As mentioned, the CQM and the CQP were created specifically for apprenticeships within the informal economy and operate independently from formal vocational qualifications. Entry requirements for the CQM are intentionally low: apprentices are not required to have completed primary school, in stark contrast to formal vocational education and training (VET) pathways. Requirements for the more advanced CQP are higher. In Benin, for example, the minimum schooling requirement has been raised from Grade 5 (end of primary education) to Grade 7 (two years of lower-secondary schooling), and candidates must pass an entrance test assessing basic French and mathematics competences. These requirements, however, are often applied flexibly in practice. The same applies to the official provision that both CQM and CQP programmes should last three years: in reality, many artisans decide themselves when to send apprentices for the examination, and this frequently occurs after more than three years of training.

A recent reform has further strengthened the permeability between (in)formal apprenticeship pathways and formal vocational education, enabling graduates to progress towards higher-level qualifications. For example, holders of the CQP are now eligible to enter technical and vocational secondary education to obtain the CAP (Certificat d'Aptitude Professionnelle), what could be best described as a professional baccalaureate which offers further options for educational mobility.

Tanzania

Apprenticeships leading to qualifications at technician and degree level

In Tanzania, apprenticeships have been introduced across multiple levels of the education system, extending beyond vocational training into higher education. Technician-level qualifications can be obtained through apprenticeship pathways, such as those offered by the National College of Tourism. After a first year – which includes approximately 60 per cent workplace learning – apprentices can attain the Basic Technician Certificate, followed by the Technician Certificate after the second year. Entry typically requires completion of O-Levels (usually at around 17 years of age). In addition, with support from the ILO, universities have begun offering apprenticeship-based programmes that lead to full Bachelor's degrees, including, for example, a Bachelor's degree in Banking and Finance.

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B) Duration of the apprenticeship

Apprenticeships can also vary significantly in terms of their duration.

- ▶ **No defined duration:** In informal apprenticeships, the length of training is often not specified and is not constrained by labour law. As a result, apprentices may remain in a subordinate, unpaid relationship with the master craftsperson for many years, with limited predictability regarding progression or completion.
- ▶ **Duration according to laws and regulations:** In many African countries, labour legislation defines the maximum or typical length of an apprenticeship for the formal sector. While these rules provide clarity, they are often difficult to implement in informal settings, where production realities and social norms shape training practices more strongly than regulatory frameworks.
- ▶ **Duration according to formal and non-formal VET regulations:** Apprenticeships that lead to formal or non-formal qualifications almost always have a defined duration. This length reflects both the complexity of the occupation and its positioning within the education and training system. The duration is therefore part of a broader qualification architecture rather than a purely workplace-based decision.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

▶ Duration of apprenticeship training – why it matters for sustainability

The duration of apprenticeship training is a decisive design choice because it directly shapes the cost-benefit balance for enterprises. In informal systems, training often has no fixed end point, allowing firms to benefit from apprentices' labour over extended periods but offering little predictability for learners. Where laws or further regulations define duration, clarity increases, yet flexibility decreases. If formally designed programmes are too long, they tend to overly raise opportunity costs for learners, leading to dropout. When, in contrast, apprenticeship programmes are too short, they become unattractive for the enterprises that want to benefit from the comparatively low apprenticeship wages. Unrealistic durations are therefore a common reason why apprenticeship pilots struggle to scale sustainably.

C) Inclusion of off-the-job training components

- ▶ **No off-the-job training.** In many small workshops, apprenticeships rely exclusively on learning through work. This option is less costly, shorter in duration and easier to organise, but it limits opportunities to teach theoretical knowledge or foundational skills. This in turn often means less mobility in the labour market and fewer linkages to further training.
- ▶ **With off-the-job training.** Some apprenticeship models include structured learning outside the workplace, for example in training centres or community facilities. The share of off-the-job training can vary considerably but compared to predominantly school-based formal VET programmes it is usually well below 50 per cent – often closer to 10 per cent. These arrangements increase costs and extend the duration of training, but they enable the systematic teaching of theory, foundational competences and broader occupational knowledge. As a result, they are more likely to lead to recognised qualifications.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Using synergies between apprenticeship and regular formal VET

Off-the-job training as part of apprenticeships can often be delivered through existing training centres or schools. This creates important synergies: such providers already have workshops, equipment and qualified instructors, making delivery more efficient and cost-effective than establishing parallel structures. Such cooperation is considerably easier when apprenticeship programmes are genuinely embedded in the TVET system and, where possible, lead to qualifications that can also be attained through more school-based training pathways.

D) Language policy

- ▶ Predominance of official languages. In many African countries, official languages such as English or French dominate vocational standards, curricula, trainer preparation, off-the-job instruction and assessment. Yet in everyday practice – especially in informal workplaces – these languages are often less widely used than national or local languages. This can limit the practical usability of training content and reduce engagement among informal sector stakeholders.
- ▶ Use of local languages. Some apprenticeship initiatives intentionally integrate national or local languages into training delivery and learning materials in order to strengthen participation and comprehension in workshops. This can facilitate stronger involvement of informal enterprises and help ensure that training tools are actually used. However, such approaches require political commitment and acceptance that the development of multilingual materials increases costs and administrative effort.

3.5 Why these choices matter for implementation

The design choices within these dimensions each come with advantages and limitations that cannot be explored in detail here. What matters is that the selected arrangements are workable in the local context and not dependent on temporary project structures, and that capacities of institutions and authorities to provide support, upgrade, recognize and improve apprenticeships are built along the way. Apprenticeships must operate in ways that participating stakeholders – especially enterprises – can sustain once external support ends.

Different stakeholders naturally gravitate towards different options: employers tend to favour solutions that are financially viable and allow them to benefit from apprentices' productive contribution, whereas social and education policy actors often prioritise access, equity and training quality. These perspectives reflect legitimate interests, yet lasting implementation requires a high degree of employer buy-in. Even where design choices are motivated primarily by educational considerations, apprenticeships will only take root if enterprises view the arrangements as attractive to them. Employers' organizations can thereby play an important role in bringing apprenticeship programs to scale by mobilizing enterprises, negotiating viable frameworks, and reducing the risk of poaching, while workers' organizations can help to ensure protection and rights, and mobilize apprentices.

Design choices across the dimensions described above have wide-ranging implications:

- ▶ They affect the feasibility of training in workshops and enterprises.
- ▶ They determine the accessibility and attractiveness of apprenticeships for different learner groups.
- ▶ They influence the costs borne by enterprises, governments and apprentices.
- ▶ They shape the programme's labour market relevance and social recognition.
- ▶ They condition how curricula, assessment procedures and support mechanisms must be designed.

Being explicit about these foundational design decisions allows policy-makers and practitioners to avoid inconsistencies – for example, designing a curriculum that cannot be delivered in typical workshops, or defining entry requirements that exclude the very groups the programme aims to support.

3.6 The key role of political objectives underlying apprenticeship policies

The design of apprenticeship programmes is never neutral. It is shaped – often decisively – by the political objectives that governments, social partners and other stakeholders attach to apprenticeships. These objectives determine which design elements receive priority, how resources are allocated and which trade-offs are considered acceptable. For reforms to be effective and sustainable, such objectives must be broadly shared, discussed through social dialogue, and realistically aligned with what enterprises, training institutions and apprentices can implement.

A) Economic policy objectives

Economic objectives frequently dominate the policy rationale for expanding apprenticeships. Governments may seek to:

- ▶ strengthen the productivity (and thereby wages) in key economic sectors, including those in rural areas where the informal economy plays a central role;
- ▶ address skills shortages in occupations that constrain productivity or growth;
- ▶ support the upgrading of informal enterprises through more structured learning, and improved working conditions and health and safety.

In many cases, the goal is not only to enhance skills development in a narrow sense, but also to increase the supply of qualified workers in occupations with persistent demand.

B) Social policy objectives

Apprenticeship reforms are also increasingly expected to contribute to social inclusion, often in view of specific disadvantaged groups, such as young women, unemployed youth, learners with weak educational backgrounds, persons with disabilities as well as migrants and forcibly displaced persons. Typical aims include:

- ▶ creating accessible and permeable pathways;
- ▶ improving equity within programmes (e.g. by lowering direct training costs or shortening the distances to training institutions);
- ▶ reducing social barriers to labour market entry.

While these objectives are legitimate, they may be less central from the perspective of enterprises. When apprenticeships are used to pursue broader social-policy goals, additional resources are usually needed and justified. For long-term sustainability, it is therefore essential to clarify early on where such funding will come from – potentially drawing on budgets from social protection, employment promotion, migration or gender policies.

Gender inclusion in apprenticeship systems

Women remain underrepresented in many apprenticeship systems, and where they do participate, they are often concentrated in a narrow set of feminised and lower-paid trades. At the same time, experience from several countries shows that gender disparities are not fixed: they respond to practical design choices, realistic incentives and clear communication. The aim is not to create parallel schemes for women, but to ensure that apprenticeship opportunities – including those in better-paid technical trades – are genuinely accessible to all.

Strengthening gender inclusion requires attention at two levels:

▶ **Level 1 – Understanding how gender shapes participation**

Before designing targeted measures, stakeholders need a clear picture of who enters which trades, under what conditions, and with what outcomes. This includes identifying where informal norms, recruitment practices or household responsibilities limit women's access. In many countries, such analysis is still limited – a missed opportunity, given how strongly gender norms influence trade choice and working conditions in both formal and informal apprenticeships.

▶ **Level 2 – Integrating gender considerations into system design, delivery and monitoring**

Gender inclusion improves when small, concrete adjustments are built into mainstream apprenticeship arrangements: clearer equality provisions in regulations; targeted outreach that challenges stereotypes; practical support such as stipends, transport or childcare; and safe learning environments with zero tolerance for harassment. Systematic monitoring and feedback allow for adjustments and continued improvements. Experience shows that such measures are most effective when they are realistic for enterprises, embedded in existing coordination structures and developed through dialogue with artisans, employers' and workers' organisations, women's groups and communities.

Benin

Encouraging girls' access to non-traditional trades

Under the Benin Youth Employment Project (PEJ), a dedicated subcomponent supported girls to enter trades traditionally dominated by men. Measures included sensitising master craftspersons, offering practical support such as childcare and providing targeted incentives to reduce the opportunity costs of participation. By project completion, women represented 53 per cent of all beneficiaries, and 470 young women had entered male-dominated occupations. The experience illustrates a pragmatic lesson: when gender measures address the real constraints faced by learners and trainers – rather than relying on broad awareness campaigns alone – they can open pathways into a wider range of trades without overburdening enterprises or creating separate systems.

C) Educational policy objectives

Educational objectives concern the role of apprenticeships within the wider learning system. Common priorities include:

- ▶ strengthening vocational pathways to counter academic drift and reduce pressure on higher-education systems;
- ▶ developing programmes that remain closely aligned with labour market needs, thereby improving relevance and employability;
- ▶ creating progression routes without turning apprenticeships into purely school-based programmes.

These objectives often require balancing permeability with labour market anchoring: pathways should be open so that learners can continue progressing and develop the skills to understand and shape their working and social environment, as set out in ILO's Human Resources Development Convention, 1975 (No. 142). At the same time, apprenticeships must be firmly rooted in real work processes and production systems to ensure they meet labour market needs. Neither objective should take precedence over the other.

Challenges and implications

Tensions between these objectives are common. For example, expanding access for vulnerable groups may require additional administrative procedures to allocate subsidies, while employers tend to favour arrangements with low administrative and financial burdens, and hence might oppose inclusion measures. Similarly, upgrading qualifications can enhance mobility but may reduce the attractiveness of apprenticeships for small enterprises if requirements become too demanding, and if perceived risk of poaching increases.

For these reasons, apprenticeship reforms benefit from a clear theory of change that explains how strengthening apprenticeships is expected to contribute to broader economic, social or educational goals – and acknowledges where the limits of apprenticeship interventions lie. Many policy challenges, such as persistent skills shortages, cannot be resolved through training alone; they also depend on working conditions, wage levels and broader labour market dynamics.

Effective apprenticeship design therefore require both ambition and realism: political objectives must guide programme design, but design choices must remain feasible for the stakeholders who ultimately carry the system – enterprises, trainers and apprentices themselves.

4. Developing occupational profiles and curricula

Occupational profiles and training curricula are central instruments in the organisation of apprenticeship systems. In the end, they define what is to be learned and how the learning process is structured, and they have considerable influence on how the training will later be recognised – both within the labour market and within the broader education and training system.

In contexts where many apprenticeships operate informally, the written definition of learning content represents one of the core steps towards formalisation. It gives visibility to the skills acquired and provides a foundation for social and professional recognition. In formal apprenticeship schemes, occupational profiles and curricula also ensure that learning outcomes are coherent across enterprises and training centres.

Benefits of content structuring

Clear occupational profiles and curricula offer multiple advantages:

- ▶ **They guide trainers and instructors**, helping them to plan and monitor learning progress;
- ▶ **They support assessment and certification**, by defining observable competences and performance criteria;
- ▶ **They provide transparency to learners**, employers and policy-makers, clarifying what an apprenticeship qualification represents.

However, these benefits are realised only when design remains closely linked to the realities of work.

Quality apprenticeships

A structured definition of occupational content is a defining feature of quality apprenticeships. Developing occupational standards therefore serves two main objectives:

- **Structuring training content** in a way that reflects occupational practice as well as market needs and supports effective learning;
- **Enhancing recognition of qualifications** and their value in the labour market.

Yet, experience across Africa shows that overly ambitious or standardised curricula can easily become counterproductive. When occupational profiles are written without regard to enterprise realities, they risk undermining the essence of work-based learning.

Common pitfalls include:

- **Excessive prescription of tasks** that cannot be performed in small enterprises or workshops;
- **Assumed access to machinery** or tools that are unavailable in local settings;
- **Technical language** or complexity that alienates artisans and master craftspersons.

Effective curricula therefore strike a balance: they provide orientation and coherence without dictating every detail of workplace practice.

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4.1 Key considerations in developing occupational profiles and curricula

With the aim of defining relevant apprenticeship content, the process of developing occupational profiles and curricula should be inclusive and firmly oriented towards practical implementation.

Key principles include:

- ▶ Strong involvement of workplace representatives. Employers, workers, master craftspersons and trade associations must participate actively in defining occupational profiles, ensuring that training reflects real production practices.
- ▶ Focus on implementation. Profiles and curricula should be achievable under typical workshop conditions, not designed for ideal scenarios.
- ▶ Accessible language and format. Simplicity supports ownership; curricula written in clear, practical terms are easier to adopt and adapt.

Good design thus combines technical precision with pedagogical pragmatism.

Ghana

Developing occupational standards with industry input

In Ghana, VET reforms led to the introduction of competency-based occupational standards developed together with industry representatives. Under the coordination of the Commission for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (CTVET), employers and master craftspersons helped define the duties and tasks forming the basis of new curricula. In several pilot sectors, these profiles were then simplified and translated into practical training tools for workshops, enabling even small informal enterprises to apply them. The process shows how curriculum development can align formal qualification objectives with workplace realities, by engaging those who understand the occupation best and by prioritising usability over technical perfection.

4.2 Commonly used methods in the design of occupational profiles and curricula

Across African countries, two main competence-based approaches are applied to define occupational profiles and curricula. Both focus on identifying and describing competences as observable abilities linked to real work situations. In practice, however, the distinction between occupational profiles and curricula is not always clear-cut. Occupational profiles generally form the core curricular foundation, because they specify the essential competences and tasks that define an occupation. Depending on the type of apprenticeship or training pathway, these profiles are then complemented by secondary curricular documents – for example, training guidelines, modular learning units or assessment plans – which elaborate the content in greater detail.

Despite these conceptual layers, the development process typically begins with the same question: what do skilled workers in this occupation need to be able to do? The competence-based methods used in the region differ in structure and formality, but all aim to answer this question in a transparent and practice-oriented way.

DACUM (Developing a Curriculum)

DACUM is a participatory method that brings together experienced workers and trainers to describe an occupation in terms of duties and tasks. The outcome is a competence matrix that summarises what practitioners must be able to do, supported by detailed task and skill statements.

The strength of DACUM lies in its clarity and usability: the matrix format is easily understood by artisans and employers alike and provides a concise visual representation of the training content. Depending on the apprenticeship pathway, the competence matrix can then be elaborated into more detailed layers – for example, into curricula for the school-based component or into enterprise training plans (see Section 3).

Approche par compétences (APC)

The Approche par compétences, widely used in Francophone Africa and promoted by the Organisation internationale de la Francophonie (OIF), builds on a similar competence-based logic but integrates more elaborate steps of pedagogical design and assessment planning. It often includes the sequencing of learning situations, evaluation tools and resource requirements.

While comprehensive, the APC approach is sometimes considered demanding in terms of expertise and documentation, and its effective application requires sustained support for trainers.

Benin

Harmonising competence-based methods in curriculum design

Benin has made deliberate efforts to integrate elements of the DACUM method with the OIF's Approche par compétences into a hybrid model known as the Approche harmonisée. This approach combines the clarity of DACUM task matrices with the more detailed pedagogical structuring typical of APC, enabling practitioners to work with a coherent yet practical framework. The hybrid process keeps the focus on workplace competences, involves employers and master craftspersons directly in defining tasks, and translates occupational standards into structured training and assessment outcomes. By harmonising the two approaches, Benin has sought to ensure usability for workshops while maintaining alignment with national curriculum standards.

4.3 The role of knowledge, foundational skills and transversal competences

The methods commonly used to develop occupational profiles – whether DACUM, the Approche par compétences or hybrid approaches – tend to focus primarily on the competences that are directly visible in workplace tasks. This is valuable, because it ensures that training is anchored in real labour market requirements. At the same time, this approach means that certain types of learning content do not automatically appear at the level of occupational profiles and must therefore be integrated later, typically at the level of curricula or training modules.

Knowledge requirements

Competent performance in an occupation generally relies not only on practical skills but also on basic vocational knowledge. This includes, for example, the correct use of technical terminology, understanding of tools and materials, or essential scientific and technical principles (such as basic electrical safety or agronomic principles).

In more formalised apprenticeship systems, curricula ensure that such knowledge is systematically addressed through off-the-job training. This is one of the areas in which formal apprenticeships typically differ from informal ones: the structure ensures that apprentices acquire the conceptual foundations that support safe, productive and adaptable work.

Foundational skills and transversal competences

A similar issue arises with foundational skills such as literacy and numeracy, and with transversal competences such as communication, problem solving, social and emotional skills or basic digital literacy (see also ILO's Core Skills for Employability framework). These competences are essential for learning at the workplace and for performing many tasks safely and reliably.

Yet, because they are not tied to specific duties or tasks, they often do not appear naturally in occupational profiles. In practice, curriculum developers must therefore identify where such skills are required and ensure that they are either integrated into learning units and assessments or clearly linked to entry requirements.

Ghana

Integrating functional mathematics into construction apprenticeships

In Ghana's construction sector, foundational numeracy has been deliberately embedded into apprenticeship training to address a recurring practical challenge: inaccurate measurements can compromise safety, quality and efficiency. Stakeholders therefore agreed that apprentices require a minimum level of functional mathematics to perform key tasks reliably. Rather than introducing abstract or school-like mathematics – which could discourage learners, many of whom fear formal maths – the programme integrates numeracy directly into occupational standards and practical learning activities. Measurement, basic calculations and task-relevant problem solving are taught in ways that feel “work-like” rather than academic, helping apprentices understand why these skills matter.

This approach ensures that foundational numeracy becomes an enabler of workplace learning rather than a barrier to participation. It also illustrates how transversal competences can be built into competence matrices and training modules without overwhelming learners or shifting the focus away from practical, production-oriented training.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Balance between workplace relevance and broader competence development

There are strong arguments for including relevant knowledge, foundational skills and transversal competences in apprenticeship training. They can deepen apprentices' understanding of their occupation, support problem solving and adaptation, and reinforce the social recognition of qualifications. Moreover, many workplace tasks rely on a minimum threshold of literacy, numeracy or ICT competence.

However, integrating such content comes with important trade-offs. The more strongly knowledge and transversal competences are emphasised, the longer and more demanding the overall programme becomes – which increases opportunity costs for learners and financial costs for providers. These elements often require dedicated training centres or structured classroom sessions, which adds to the complexity of implementation.

Overemphasis on broad competences may also shift the orientation of apprenticeships towards general education and progression pathways, potentially weakening their labour market focus. Policy makers and practitioners therefore need to find a balance between workplace relevance and broader competence development.

Addressing foundational skills: practical options

Experience across countries shows that foundational skills requirements must be addressed in one way or another. A few practical options exist:

- ▶ Foundational skills are assumed but not supported. Programmes rely on basic education systems and do not include additional measures.
- ▶ Foundational skills are required and supported through bridging arrangements. Learners without sufficient literacy or numeracy may complete preparatory courses before entering an apprenticeship or receive targeted support during training. R208 recommends this approach through pre-apprenticeship programmes.
- ▶ Foundational skills form part of off-the-job training. Programmes integrate literacy, numeracy or digital skills into classroom-based components (further discussed in Section 4).

The choice between these options depends on the target group, the structure of the training system and resource availability. What matters is that the issue is acknowledged explicitly, since foundational skills are closely linked to learning success and retention.

Senegal

Limits of integrating foundational learning in informal apprenticeships

In Senegal, informal apprenticeships often focus strongly on practical production skills, with limited systematic attention to vocational knowledge, literacy or numeracy. Several programmes attempted to introduce basic training modules delivered in training centres, yet uptake remained low due to time constraints, travel distance and the opportunity costs for apprentices and workshops. In fact, many master craftspersons recognise the importance of literacy and theoretical understanding, but struggle to allocate time for structured teaching alongside production demands. The experience shows that integrating foundational competences requires not only curriculum design, but also realistic delivery arrangements, otherwise these elements remain aspirational rather than transformative.

5. Supporting the quality of work-based learning

5.1 Balancing quality expectations with enterprise realities

There is broad consensus – among policy-makers, training specialists and international organisations – on what constitutes quality in work-based learning. Core elements typically include:

- ▶ Decent working conditions, including occupational safety and health, fair treatment and respect for labour rights
- ▶ A work environment that supports learning, where apprentices have opportunities to practise a broad range of tasks, receive meaningful guidance and are not simply used as cheap labour

These principles also underpin the ILO's Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208) and provide an important reference for system development and reform.

However, translating these expectations into practice is not straightforward, especially in low-income and informal economies where most enterprises operate under financial pressure. Enterprises are, first and foremost, economic actors. Their willingness to train is shaped by commercial considerations, productivity demands and immediate cost-benefit calculations. For this reason, supporting workplace training often requires a degree of pragmatism and compromise, particularly in early stages of system development.

Many existing apprenticeship arrangements fall short of established quality standards – for reasons that are structural rather than intentional:

- ▶ Informal apprenticeships often lack regulated working conditions and may involve long hours, unpaid labour or even child labour.
- ▶ Apprenticeships governed by labour law or others may comply with regulations, but still provide little structured training, functioning primarily as a contractual form of employment.

These realities do not invalidate the ambition to improve training quality. Instead, they highlight that incremental progress may be more effective than attempting to enforce ideal standards from the outset.

In contexts where training practices are still evolving, flexible and context-sensitive solutions are often more likely to gain acceptance among enterprises and ultimately lead to sustainable improvements.

The following sections therefore present approaches that seek to strengthen the quality of work-based learning while acknowledging the real constraints under which enterprises operate. The goal is not to lower standards, but to identify feasible entry points that can gradually build commitment to training and allow quality to increase over time.

Senegal

Strengthening apprenticeships through better working conditions

In Senegal, the formal VET system is well established, but remains largely disconnected from the informal apprenticeship sector, where most young people learn their trades. Unlike Benin or Côte d'Ivoire, Senegal has not yet introduced qualifications such as the CQM or CQP that could formalise learning in informal workshops. Instead, reforms have for many years focused on improving the working conditions of apprentices – for example, through clearer rules on hours, safety and remuneration. This pragmatic strategy acknowledges that, in the short term, improving the daily realities of apprentices may have a greater impact than introducing qualifications that workshops are not yet prepared to use. The new Sector Policy 2025-29, however, foresees certification for apprentices in dualized apprenticeships.

5.2 Key elements of work-based learning

Work-based learning in apprenticeship programmes typically combines several distinct but interrelated learning processes. While these occur in both formal and informal systems, the balance and level of structure differ significantly depending on the degree of programme formalisation.

Element 1: Learning through work (on-the-job learning)

This is the core component of most apprenticeships and often takes place in a highly informal manner.

Form 1: Learning through modelling

In this form of learning, apprentices work alongside the instructor or master craftsperson during real production tasks. They acquire skills by observing, imitating and gradually copying expert performance. This process reflects the classic “watch and follow” or “show and do” approach, where learning is embedded directly in productive work.

Form 2: Learning through guided experience

Once basic skills have been acquired, apprentices increasingly learn by carrying out tasks independently. Competence develops through practice, repetition and problem solving, and mistakes become part of the learning process. Skill development therefore takes place primarily through experience rather than explicit instruction.

Element 2: Instruction

Instruction refers to the deliberate explanation and demonstration of tools, techniques and work processes, usually delivered at the workplace but outside the immediate workflow. The instructor or master craftsperson typically presents a complete task, highlights critical steps, points out risks and introduces the relevant professional terminology. In practice, instruction frequently overlaps with modelling, especially in informal settings where formal teaching practices are limited. Increasingly, digital resources such as YouTube® tutorials are used to complement instruction and provide learners with demonstrations that may not be available locally.

In some apprenticeship models, the instructional component is strengthened at the beginning of training and delivered in a training centre before apprentices enter the workplace (see Section 6 on off-the-job training).

Element 3: Feedback

Feedback allows apprentices to understand whether their performance meets expected standards.

- ▶ Informal feedback is the most common form, provided verbally during or after work activities.
- ▶ Formalised feedback may involve structured review meetings, the use of logbooks or formative assessment.

Element 4: Reflection

Reflection helps apprentices make sense of their learning process and generalise insights beyond individual tasks. It also provides an important foundation for developing transversal competences – such as problem solving and social skills – that support effective workplace learning and professional growth.

- ▶ Informal reflection occurs spontaneously through conversation and self-evaluation.
- ▶ Formal reflection is facilitated when training systems include structured review sessions, journals or guided discussions.

Quality apprenticeships

The more formalised an apprenticeship becomes, the more explicitly all four elements – **instruction, feedback and reflection alongside on-the-job learning** – are integrated. In contrast, informal apprenticeships typically rely almost entirely on learning through work, with explicit instruction, feedback and reflection occurring implicitly rather than intentionally.

5.3 Developing an enterprise training plan

A core feature of quality apprenticeships is the structured organisation of learning in the workplace. While the degree of structure varies depending on the apprenticeship model (see Chapter 3), most programmes benefit from having a clear, written document that outlines what an apprentice should learn in the enterprise. In this Guidance Note, this document is referred to as an enterprise training plan.

Enterprise training plans can take very different forms depending on the level of formalisation, the enterprise environment and the pedagogical capacities of trainers. In some systems they are short, highly practical tools; in others, they are more detailed documents aligned with national curricula or occupational profiles. Despite this variation, several common principles apply.

5.3.1 Purpose and added value of enterprise training plans

- ▶ They translate occupational profiles or curricula into concrete learning activities for the workshop or enterprise.
- ▶ They provide orientation for trainers and apprentices, helping ensure that key practical tasks are covered during the apprenticeship period.
- ▶ They help make workplace learning more intentional and transparent, rather than dependent solely on day-to-day production needs.
- ▶ They create a basis for monitoring learning progress, particularly when combined with apprentices' self-documentation (e.g. through logbooks).

For many master craftspersons and small enterprises – especially in the informal economy – such tools can be the first step towards making training more structured without undermining the flexibility that characterises apprenticeship systems in the informal economy.

5.3.2 Design considerations

1. Clarity and usability

Enterprise training plans must be easy to read and understand, especially in contexts where trainers have limited formal education or pedagogical training. The language should be simple, concrete and directly linked to everyday work tasks. Short, visual or tabular formats are often more effective than text-heavy documents.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Competence matrices

Competence matrices present the key duties and tasks of an occupation in a concise tabular format, allowing trainers and apprentices to see at a glance what should be learned. In many systems, they function as a condensed representation of the occupational profile and thus serve as a core curricular reference. At the same time, they can be used as a practical communication tool to summarise essential training content for enterprises, offering a simpler alternative to a detailed training plan, particularly in apprenticeship contexts that are short, informal or constrained in resources.

2. Realistic implementation

Training plans should reflect what is actually feasible in typical workshops and enterprises. This includes:

- ▶ **the type of tasks that are realistically performed**
- ▶ **the tools and materials commonly available**
- ▶ **the time constraints of production environments**
- ▶ **the capacity and experience of trainers**

Plans that list tasks or requirements that most workshops cannot fulfil risk undermining the credibility of the apprenticeship model.

3. Alignment with occupational profiles and curricula

Where occupational profiles or national curricula exist, the enterprise training plan should connect to them in a simple and practical way. The plan operationalises the broader training standards and helps ensure coherence between workplace learning, any off-the-job modules and assessment expectations.

4. Managing with the sequence of training content

In school-based training programmes, the sequence of learning content is typically defined in advance and applied uniformly across institutions. Curricula specify not only what should be taught, but also the order in which knowledge and skills are introduced. This level of standardisation, however, is rarely feasible in apprenticeship systems where most learning takes place in enterprises.

Workplaces differ greatly in terms of equipment, production cycles, customer demands and seasonal variations. Even within the same enterprise, the types of tasks carried out will vary over time. For this reason, enterprise training plans need to allow for flexible implementation. Rather than prescribing a fixed sequence, they should define the core tasks and competences to be covered during the apprenticeship, while leaving trainers free to adjust the order in which these elements are addressed.

Uganda

Structured workplace learning aligned with modular school-based training

Uganda's hotel-sector apprenticeships exemplify a highly formalised, industry-led approach to work-based learning. Apprentices complete a one-year programme that closely links workplace phases with defined school-based modules delivered by a training institute. After an initial month of general theory, apprentices rotate through all hotel departments before specialising, with on-the-job tasks aligned to the curriculum.

Given the dynamic nature of the hospitality sector, the curriculum is regularly reviewed to ensure labour-market relevance. Employers play a central role by identifying emerging skills needs and operational changes. Workplace supervisors receive dedicated training and use standardised training plans and logbooks. While pedagogically effective, this model limits enterprise autonomy and requires strong employer commitment.

Benin

Flexible enterprise training built around competence matrices

In Benin's CQM pathway, all training takes place directly in workshops, without any off-the-job component. Master craftspersons rely on a DACUM-based competence matrix as their main guidance tool, but retain full autonomy over when and how each competence is taught. This flexibility aligns well with real production rhythms and makes the system highly attractive for enterprises, who can integrate apprentices into daily work without rigid sequencing requirements. It has also encouraged many artisans to participate in the formalisation of training, since they are not constrained by prescriptive curricula. For the more advanced CQP level, however, the content requirements are substantially more detailed and structured, reflecting the higher expected level of professional competence.

Such flexibility ensures that learning can take place in alignment with real production processes and not in contradiction to them. It also enables apprentices to benefit from authentic work situations as they arise, while still maintaining a structured approach to skill acquisition.

5.4 Trainers and master craftspersons: Requirements and training

Well-prepared trainers and master craftspersons are central to the quality of work-based learning. Across most interventions, expectations typically include three core components:

- ▶ a minimum level of general education or literacy
- ▶ occupational expertise in the relevant trade
- ▶ pedagogical or instructional competences to support learning

Yet, in many African countries, the starting point for trainer qualification is shaped by the realities of the informal economy. In fact, trainers often have many years of practical experience, but limited formal education, sometimes with low literacy levels, and no formal occupational certificate, even if they are highly competent in practice.

Therefore, programmes seeking to strengthen workplace learning must remain aware that raising requirements too high may undermine participation and sustainability. In many contexts, it is unrealistic to assume that large numbers of enterprises will be willing or able to invest in extensive training for trainers or meet high entry requirements. A realistic objective is therefore not to enforce ideal standards from the outset, but to move one or more steps beyond current reality, in a way that is feasible and context-appropriate. Trade associations, chambers, and workers' and employers' organizations play a role in outreach, awareness creation and support upskilling of trainers and master craftspersons.

Component 1: Addressing gaps in general education and literacy

- ▶ In many contexts, it must be accepted that trainers have limited formal education.

Where basic literacy is required for training tasks (e.g. filling logbooks), functional literacy courses can be offered as a support measure – not as a precondition for participation.

Component 2: Occupational qualification

- ▶ Few artisans and master craftspersons hold formal vocational qualifications, and this is often not the main barrier to effective training.
- ▶ However, formalising their status can strengthen the credibility of apprenticeship programmes and increase trainer motivation.
- ▶ In several countries, Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) has therefore been used to allow artisans to obtain the same qualification awarded to apprentices after completion – or a different one (see also Section 7.2).
- ▶ This can be a useful solution, but only if accompanied by reliable assessment tools to ensure that trainers genuinely possess the skills that apprentices are expected to learn.

Benin and Côte d'Ivoire

Different approaches to master craftsperson qualification pathways

As outlined above (see 3.1), both Benin and Côte d'Ivoire use the CQM and CQP to support the formalisation of apprenticeships in the informal sector. A key difference lies not in the function of the CQP itself, but in how experienced master craftspersons access it. In Côte d'Ivoire, the CQP is widely used across different non-formal qualification pathways and is also awarded through Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), allowing experienced artisans to obtain formal recognition of their competences. Because many master craftspersons have limited formal schooling, admission requirements are often applied flexibly in practice. In Benin, by contrast, access to the CQP is more closely tied to structured training pathways and is increasingly oriented towards progression into further education. These differing practices shape how the CQP functions within each country's apprenticeship system.

Component 3: Pedagogical preparation

Most initiatives provide some form of training-of-trainers, typically delivered in project settings. These often include:

- ▶ Basic principles of adult learning (andragogy)
- ▶ Understanding the training plan or curriculum
- ▶ Use of training tools such as logbooks

However, experience shows that such courses are frequently:

- ▶ Too theoretical and not sufficiently connected to real workplace challenges
- ▶ Delivered in unfamiliar language or terminology (e.g. French in parts of West Africa), which limits interaction
- ▶ Targeted not at the actual instructors but to their superiors who do not directly work with the apprentices.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Pedagogical preparation of workplace trainers

Skilled master craftspersons and instructors are essential – but experience from diverse apprenticeship initiatives shows that pedagogical preparation is most effective when introduced gradually and with a strong focus on practical application. Trainers benefit from short, highly targeted courses that emphasise clarity and immediate usefulness rather than abstract theory. A brief introductory block typically covers the structure of the apprenticeship, the trainer’s role as well as key information about occupational health and safety. After several months of workplace experience, follow-up sessions can provide space for reflection, peer learning and exchange on real challenges encountered in training apprentices. This staged, hands-on approach helps trainers build confidence over time, supports the gradual integration of new practices into everyday routines and avoids overwhelming them before they have had a chance to apply what they learn.

Tanzania

Strengthening trainers through structured ToT requirements

In Tanzania, the professionalisation of workplace trainers has become an increasingly explicit priority within apprenticeship reforms. Enterprises participating in more formalised apprenticeship schemes – such as those linked to the National College of Tourism – are expected to appoint trainers who have completed a recognised Training of Trainers (ToT) programme. These ToT courses, offered by VETA or sectoral training institutions, equip workplace instructors with basic pedagogical skills, including how to demonstrate tasks systematically, guide practice, assess learning progress and use simple training tools such as logbooks or task checklists. Although not all enterprises meet these expectations consistently (and although it has been difficult to organise such training since the outbreak of COVID-19), the requirement helps raise the training capacity of workplaces and creates a shared understanding of instructional quality. The Tanzanian experience shows how ToT obligations can serve as a pragmatic lever to improve training without imposing overly demanding academic requirements on enterprises.

5.5 Developing instructional and learning materials

Instructional and learning materials can strengthen the quality of work-based learning by helping apprentices understand key concepts, structure their learning and connect practical experience to broader occupational competences. However, such materials only have value if they are usable in the real conditions of enterprises and training centres, and if they match the linguistic, cultural and economic contexts in which they are applied.

5.5.1 The “Keeping it simple” imperative

Many apprenticeship reforms in Africa have introduced different types of instructional material (see examples below). Experience across the six countries studied shows that these tools can make workplace learning more intentional and visible – but only when they are kept simple, relevant and locally accessible.

To increase uptake and relevance, instructional tools should be:

- ▶ Low-cost, lightweight and easily reproduced
- ▶ Highly visual, using tables, diagrams and examples rather than long text
- ▶ Modular, so sections can be used independently depending on the workflow
- ▶ Designed with and not just for trainers, to ensure ownership and relevance
- ▶ Field-tested and revised based on feedback from real workshops

Quality apprenticeships

In contexts where resources are scarce and formal training infrastructure is limited, **perfect materials that remain unused are less valuable than simple tools that actually support learning.**

5.5.2 Practical tools to support structured workplace learning

A) Logbooks

Logbooks allow apprentices to document the tasks they have carried out on a daily or weekly basis and to reflect on what went well, what did not, and why. Trainers can use this record to monitor progress, identify learning gaps and plan next steps. Because they are easy to integrate into everyday work routines and require only minimal levels of literacy, logbooks are well suited to a wide range of apprenticeship settings, including those in the informal economy. They strengthen supervision and feedback, support monitoring and assessment, and help turn routine production tasks into intentional learning experiences.

Uganda

Using logbooks to structure training and strengthen reflective learning

Ugandan apprenticeship pilots introduced structured logbooks in which apprentices record the tasks completed each week and briefly reflect on challenges encountered. Trainers and workplace supervisors review the entries, verify progress, and use them to plan subsequent learning steps. Beyond their reflective function, the logbooks play a critical role in standardising workplace training by clearly outlining required competencies and tasks. This ensures that all apprentices receive comparable, structured training regardless of whether they are placed in five-star or three-star hotels. This standardisation is essential in enhancing apprentices' competitiveness in the labour market, as it assures prospective employers that graduates have attained a consistent baseline of skills and practical experience. The logbook routine strengthens reflective learning without demanding high levels of literacy, improves transparency, and makes learning outcomes visible—an important added value in contexts where workplace training might otherwise be informal, uneven, or loosely organised.

B) Standardised task sheets

Standardised task sheets are a practical tool for structuring on-the-job learning and strengthening instruction in apprenticeships. They define step by step what constitutes competent task performance – for example, procedures for mise-en-place, cleaning routines or guest interaction in hospitality. By making expectations explicit, they help harmonise training across enterprises, guide instructors and apprentices, and support targeted preparation for assessments. Experiences from several countries indicate that such sheets are most effective when kept short, visual and directly linked to workplace practice. They also help trainers with limited pedagogical experience provide clearer guidance and monitor learning progress more systematically.

C) Material on occupational safety and health

Quality apprenticeships depend not only on good training content but also on safe learning conditions. In many African contexts, workplace safety remains a major challenge – especially in small workshops and the informal economy. Strengthening Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) instruction should therefore be a core component of any effort to design and upgrade apprenticeship programmes. Training materials thereby play a key role.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Strengthening occupational safety and health (OSH) in apprenticeships

Effective approaches to strengthen OSH instruction focus on clear, practical and accessible training materials that speak directly to everyday risks. Visual and demonstration-based resources, including short digital modules or videos shared through social media, can help overcome low literacy levels and ensure that essential messages reach trainers and apprentices alike.

However, producing good materials is not enough: they must be actively used in enterprises. Collaboration with trade associations is often crucial, as these organisations can mobilise master craftsmen, promote consistent practices across workshops and reinforce norms around safe and decent training environments.

5.5.3 Language as a key design choice

Language is one of the most decisive factors for the usability of learning materials. This is particularly evident in West Africa, where:

- ▶ French is the official language of administration and vocational training systems
- ▶ Most workplace communication, however, takes place in national or local languages, including Fon, Wolof, Bambara, Dioula, Ewe and many others
- ▶ Many master craftspersons and apprentices have limited literacy in French – even if they speak it orally to some extent

As a result, materials written in French often remain unused, misunderstood or simply unavailable at workshop level. Effective strategies observed in practice include:

- ▶ Using very simple French and avoiding technical jargon
- ▶ Combining French text with visuals, diagrams and icons
- ▶ Producing bilingual versions where French is used for official purposes and local languages for explanation and discussion
- ▶ Allowing trainers to localise terminology rather than enforcing standard translations
- ▶ Providing audio or video versions in local languages

In fully informal systems, it may be more effective to accept that materials will circulate orally, supported by demonstrations, rather than to rely on written documentation. To support the inclusion of apprentices with disabilities, material in braille, screen readers or other technology-assisted devices can also improve accessibility.

5.5.4 Digital materials: potential and limits

Digital learning resources – particularly video tutorials – are increasingly used by young apprentices across Africa, often informally via YouTube or social media. They can complement traditional instruction, especially when they are available in locally understood languages and when they demonstrate real tasks using locally available tools.

However, digital tools should not be assumed to replace written or face-to-face instruction. They work best when embedded in a broader system of training support. It is also essential to recognise the digital divide: in some contexts, many apprentices have limited or no access to suitable devices – such as smartphones or computers – even when training content can be downloaded.

6. Defining off-the-job training components

ILO's R208 includes off-the-job training as defining element of quality apprenticeship programmes. In reality, however, off-the-job training is not a feature of all apprenticeships. Many apprenticeships – especially those rooted in informal economies – operate entirely through learning embedded in day-to-day production. In efforts to strengthen apprenticeships and move gradually towards quality apprenticeships, off-the-job components therefore gain increasing significance. They enable the structured teaching of knowledge and skills that are difficult to acquire solely through learning in the workplace.

6.1 Objectives and content focus

Off-the-job training can serve different objectives depending on programme design, occupational requirements and target groups.

▶ Vocational knowledge

Off-the-job training frequently focuses on vocational knowledge that underpins competent workplace performance. This includes basic trade theory, technical terminology, understanding of materials and tools, safety principles, and elementary technical or scientific concepts relevant to the occupation. Such content can usually be delivered in classroom-based settings without specialised infrastructure. Trade theory is particularly important where apprenticeships lead to recognised qualifications. Compared to practical training, this component is relatively cost-efficient to organise.

▶ Vocational skills

In many apprenticeship models, off-the-job training also includes the teaching of practical vocational skills. School- or centre-based workshops can be used to introduce techniques in a structured way, allow repeated practice, and ensure exposure to tasks that may not occur regularly in all enterprises. This can support more systematic skill development and, where well aligned with workplace realities, enhance apprentices' productivity. However, practical off-the-job training requires equipment, consumables and qualified instructors, and becomes increasingly costly as skills become more advanced and specialised.

▶ Foundational and general competences

Only rarely does off-the-job training focus primarily on literacy, numeracy or broader life skills. Yet in some contexts, these competences are regarded as essential prerequisites for successful workplace learning, particularly for youth with limited schooling (see Section 4.5). Their inclusion increases training duration and costs but may improve employability and social recognition of the qualification.

In most cases, off-the-job training combines vocational knowledge and selected vocational skills, with foundational competences added where necessary. The challenge for programme design lies in balancing educational value, labour-market relevance and financial feasibility.

6.2 Making off-the-job training work

What constitutes 'effective' off-the-job training as part of apprenticeships depends partly on stakeholder perspective. Some see it as a springboard for future learning and upward mobility in the education system; employers value its contribution to productivity and work readiness.

Yet, in the context of apprenticeship, off-the-job training is most likely to function effectively when:

- ▶ it delivers clear added value in terms of productivity and/or the social recognition of the qualification;
- ▶ it logically connects to workplace learning and provides space to reflect about workplace practice, delivering additional relevant knowledge and skills;
- ▶ instructors are well prepared and aware of workplace realities;
- ▶ facilities provide appropriate tools and equipment;
- ▶ and long-term financing is secured.

Where these conditions are not met, off-the-job training risks remaining under-used, unsustainable or disconnected from workplace learning.

Quality apprenticeships

Off-the-job training can significantly enhance the credibility of apprenticeships and strengthen skill acquisition by providing structured, standardised learning that may be difficult to achieve in workshops alone. Where well designed, it not only deepens apprentices' competences but also boosts their productivity in enterprises. In many contexts, integrating off-the-job components is therefore desirable — yet it must be organised in ways that create tangible value for both apprentices and employers.

6.3 Organisational decisions

As with apprenticeships more broadly, the design of off-the-job training also requires important organisational decisions. In the following, we discuss five key dimensions that shape these choices.

A) Share of off-the-job training

The proportion of off-the-job learning cannot be determined in isolation from context. Generally, the more complex the occupation and the higher the qualification level, the more extensive the off-the-job component. In Tanzania, for example, apprenticeships at technician level in the tourism sector include around 40 per cent off-the-job instruction, while this ratio in apprenticeships leading to the CQP in Benin and Côte d'Ivoire is lower (at 20 and 25 per cent respectively).

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B) Timing

Off-the-job training is often organised in blocks, allowing alternation between periods of instruction and phases of workplace practice. Other models distribute contact time on a weekly or monthly basis. Block models are particularly common in informal contexts, as they require less continuous coordination between enterprises and training providers and can be aligned with production cycles.

Where public training facilities exist, off-the-job training as part of apprenticeship programmes is sometimes scheduled during vacation periods or other idle times of more centre-based forms of VET, making pragmatic use of available infrastructure. Such cooperation is considerably facilitated – including with regard to budgeting – when apprenticeship programmes are integrated as one training pathway within the overall VET system.

C) Location

The choice of training sites is one of the most decisive design questions – and one of the most challenging. Local provision reduces direct and indirect costs for apprentices and allows them to remain with their families. However, reaching dispersed populations increases the number of centres required and raises operating costs. Centralised training facilities may be more efficient but imply higher costs for transport. Some countries mitigate this by focusing local delivery on foundational skills (e.g. literacy and numeracy), making use of schools or community facilities.

Ghana

Localising off-the-job training to reduce learner costs

In Ghana's construction-sector apprenticeships, off-the-job training is often delivered through short, locally organised sessions held in community facilities, vocational schools or district-level training centres. This decentralised approach reduces transport costs and allows apprentices to continue living with their families — a decisive factor in retaining low-income learners. Trainers highlight that bringing instruction closer to where apprentices live increases attendance and makes it easier to integrate essential skills such as basic mathematics, which are difficult to teach in busy workshops. At the same time, maintaining multiple local sites raises logistical and staffing demands, limiting the scope of theoretical content that can realistically be offered. The Ghanaian experience illustrates the trade-off between accessibility and resource constraints, showing how local delivery can strengthen participation but requires careful prioritisation of training content.

D) Role of training centres

Across systems, the role of schools or training centres can differ substantially:

Training centres with a complementary role.

In many apprenticeship programmes, the institutional component is secondary. Schools or training centres provide theoretical instruction alongside workplace learning, but play only a limited role in coordination or supervision. The primary responsibility for training remains with enterprises (e.g. cases from Ghana, Benin, Côte d'Ivoire).

Training centres with a coordinating role.

In other models, the school or training centre functions as the central coordinating body. It brings together the different components of training, monitors learning progress in enterprises, and has a key role in the training of instructors and master craftspersons. In such cases, the training institution becomes the backbone of the apprenticeship system (e.g. cases from Tanzania, Uganda).

Tanzania

Training centres as the backbone of apprenticeship coordination

In Tanzania's hospitality apprenticeships, the National College of Tourism (NCT) plays a central coordinating role that goes far beyond classroom instruction. The college structures the entire training process, aligns enterprise-based learning with curriculum modules, assigns apprentices to hotels, monitors workplace implementation and supports instructors through regular guidance. This integrated model ensures consistency across training sites and enables strong links between theory and practice.

E) Management of equipment

The availability of equipment is critical for off-the-job training, particularly when training covers vocational skills and not only trade theory. Experience shows that costly machinery in training centres frequently remains underused or poorly maintained in such settings. An alternative model places equipment management closer to production realities. In Benin, Senegal and Zimbabwe for example, business or trade associations manage shared equipment through technology or service centres, ensuring higher utilisation, relevance to local work practices and stronger incentives for maintenance. Such arrangements can improve cost-effectiveness and alignment with labour-market needs, provided governance responsibilities are clearly defined.

F) Financing and sustainability

Off-the-job provision is often one of the more expensive components of apprenticeships. Sustainable financing is crucial. Options include public funding, cost-sharing with enterprises, development partner support or contributions from learners (i.e. in the form of tuition fees). However, when learners must finance training directly, access for disadvantaged youth will be limited, unless stipends exist. Balancing affordability and sustainability is therefore essential.

7. Assessment and evaluation options

Assessment and evaluation are central to strengthening the credibility of apprenticeships, and empowering learners to gain confidence and progress. When competences are assessed in a structured way – ideally leading to a recognised qualification – employers gain a reliable signal of minimum skill levels, and authorities obtain a basis for monitoring and improving training quality over time. ILO Recommendation concerning the transition from the informal to the formal economy, 2015 (No. 204) calls for skills development policies that recognize prior learning such as through informal apprenticeship systems, thereby broadening options for formal employment.

Assessment practices exist even in many informal apprenticeship systems, particularly in the crafts sector, where final evaluations are long-standing traditions. Yet these assessments often do not lead to formally recognised qualifications, meaning that most apprentices across African countries complete their training without an official certificate. At the same time, many sectors with substantial on-the-job learning – such as hospitality, construction or parts of manufacturing – have no tradition of concluding apprenticeships with a formal assessment at all.

As a result, the starting point for strengthening assessment systems varies greatly across sectors and countries. In some areas, long-established informal assessment practices can be built upon; in others, introducing assessment requires new instruments, institutions and forms of cooperation.

Quality apprenticeships

To safeguard the credibility of apprenticeship outcomes, assessments should – wherever possible – involve some form of independent assessment personnel. Independence helps reinforce fairness and reduces the risk of evaluations being influenced by workshop-level interests. At the same time, especially for the assessment of practical competences, assessors must themselves have substantial, up-to-date experience in the relevant trade.

7.1 Designing assessment and evaluation processes

Across African apprenticeship systems, assessment models differ significantly. Important design dimensions include the following.

A) Content focus

The focus of assessment is closely tied to the type and level of qualification to which an apprenticeship leads (see Section 3.4), and it generally follows from what is defined in the occupational profiles and training plans. Nevertheless, it is important to specify clearly, within the context of apprenticeship design, what is actually being assessed.

Practical skills and competences

In most apprenticeship systems, particularly in the informal economy, assessments focus primarily on practical performance. This reflects the nature of workplace-based learning and the expectations of employers, who prioritise the apprentice's ability to carry out tasks safely and productively from day one. Practical tests therefore remain the backbone of assessment in many trades.

Knowledge and theoretical understanding

Where apprenticeships lead to qualifications recognised within the education system – and especially where they open pathways to further learning – assessments most often also cover vocational knowledge and theoretical understanding (“trade theory”). This includes concepts, terminology, underpinning principles and rules of safe practice. Such components are typically assessed in written or oral formats, or through combined practical-theoretical tasks.

Transversal skills and competences

Across education systems, there is growing interest in assessing transversal competences such as communication, problem solving or self-management. In formal VET, these elements are only occasionally assessed explicitly.

In apprenticeships in the informal economy, however, broader dimensions of competence already play an important – albeit informal – role: master craftspersons often evaluate work ethic, trustworthiness, professional identity and reputation within the trade. These aspects matter greatly for employability, but they are difficult to assess objectively and should be handled with caution when integrating them into formal assessment systems.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

Balancing theory and practice in VET assessment for learners from the informal sector

A credible VET qualification is usually achieved through an assessment process that includes at least practical competence and some trade theory. For apprentices from the informal sector, who may have limited foundational skills in literacy and numeracy, assessments with a strong theoretical focus can – depending on their design – constitute barriers that are difficult to overcome. Against this background, assessment processes that include theory need to address the question of how large the theoretical component should be. If, for example, theory accounts for only 10% of the final mark while the overall pass mark is set at 75%, limited theoretical knowledge can be compensated for by strong practical performance – while ensuring that occupational safety and health remains a focus for all.

B) Assessment methods

The choice of assessment methods is closely tied to the content focus of the examination. Where practical skills and competences are central, assessments rely primarily on performance-based approaches; where theoretical knowledge or transversal skills are expected, additional methods become necessary.

Practical skills tests

Practical performance remains at the heart of assessment in apprenticeship systems. In practice, however, such tests take very different forms. They may range from narrow, task-specific assignments that evaluate isolated techniques to holistic workpiece productions that require apprentices to demonstrate multiple competences in an integrated manner.

Many systems attempt to increase objectivity by defining clear performance criteria and observable indicators. Yet these efforts inevitably reach their limits: the quality of a product or work process ultimately requires expert judgement, drawing on years of practical experience.

Written assessments

Written tests are primarily used when knowledge or theoretical understanding forms part of the qualification. They are less common in traditional apprenticeships, partly because they risk excluding apprentices with weak literacy skills.

Oral assessments

Oral examinations are increasingly used to complement practical tests. They allow apprentices to explain work processes, demonstrate understanding and reflect on decision-making. Oral methods can also serve as an alternative to written tests, enabling the assessment of theoretical knowledge without discriminating against illiterate or semi-literate learners.

Benin

Using CQM task sheets to structure practical and oral assessments

In Benin's CQM examinations, standardised task sheets play a central role in ensuring that assessments remain anchored in real workplace practice while retaining a minimum degree of structure. During practical tests, these sheets specify the required task (e.g. assembling a simple wooden frame or repairing a basic electrical connection), outline expected steps and list observable performance indicators. Assessors use them as reference points when judging the quality of workpieces and work processes, while still relying on their professional experience for the final judgement. In many cases, the same sheets also inform short oral assessments conducted in workshops, where apprentices are asked to explain key steps, justify choices or identify risks. This combination helps maintain fairness without undermining the flexibility of informal-sector training.

C) Timing and sequencing

How assessments are sequenced over the course of an apprenticeship has important implications for feasibility, learning support and the credibility of certification. Three broad models can be distinguished:

Final examinations

A common approach in which apprentices are assessed only once at the end of their training, focusing on the final competences defined in occupational standards. Final examinations are comparatively easy to organise administratively, though results may be influenced by day-to-day performance variation.

Continuous assessment

Used increasingly in systems where competences are modularised and assessed progressively throughout training. This model supports ongoing feedback, early identification of learning gaps and closer alignment between learning and assessment. At the same time, this approach has limitations: when assessments focus mostly on discrete units, the overall competence expected at the end of the apprenticeship may receive less attention, and the coherence of the full occupational profile can weaken.

Mixed models

Some arrangements combine both approaches, allowing formative checks during training while retaining a cumulative end-of-programme assessment.

D) Assessment personnel

The question of who conducts assessments is central – and often contentious – because it sits at the heart of the trade-off between objectivity and efficiency.

Artisans and master craftspersons

In many informal apprenticeship systems, assessments are carried out by the artisans who trained the apprentices. With years of experience and deep familiarity with workplace realities, they are generally well positioned to judge the quality of work and whether an apprentice can perform competently. However, concerns arise when apprenticeship systems become more formalised. Stakeholders often call for assessors who are not only skilled workers but also trained in applying assessment criteria consistently and independently, rather than relying mainly on personal beliefs or workshop-specific practices.

External assessors

To enhance objectivity and credibility, many systems thus introduce assessors from outside the training enterprise. These can come from different types of organisations:

Quality apprenticeships

To ensure the credibility of apprenticeships, independent assessment personnel should be involved wherever possible. At the same time, this personnel – especially when practical competences are being assessed – should themselves possess substantial experience in the relevant field.

▶ Trade associations

In several countries, professional bodies play a central role in end-of-apprenticeship examinations. Given their limited staff, associations often nominate experienced master craftspersons to assess apprentices trained in other workshops – reducing direct dependency and increasing perceived fairness.

▶ Public authorities and training institutions

In more formalised systems, responsibility for assessment lies increasingly with government bodies, sometimes supported by dedicated assessment centres or training institutions. While this tends to strengthen objectivity, it comes with a different risk: assessments may gradually be conducted by individuals with less workplace experience, especially if qualification requirements for assessors become too high for practising master craftspersons to meet.

The choice of assessment location is closely linked to earlier design decisions, yet it warrants explicit consideration because it can significantly affect candidates' costs, accessibility and perceived fairness.

Senegal

Mixed examination juries in apprenticeship assessment

In Senegal's apprenticeship reforms, end-of-training examinations are conducted by mixed juries composed of representatives from training institutions, public authorities and professional associations. This composition is intended to strengthen credibility by combining pedagogical expertise, regulatory oversight and practical experience from the crafts sector. It also reduces the risk that assessments reflect only the practices of individual workshops. At the same time, the model generates notable costs: jurors must be mobilised and compensated, examinations often take place in centralised locations, and apprentices and their families face travel and subsistence expenses. These financial and logistical demands have become a recurring challenge, yet the mixed-jury model continues to be viewed as an important safeguard for fairness and transparency.

Assessment centres or schools

This is the classical model used in many trade tests (see below). Centralised assessment facilities help standardise conditions and create a level playing field for all candidates. However, they often entail substantial costs for apprentices — including travel, accommodation, examiner fees and material expenses — which can deter low-income candidates. In some trades, such as plumbing and electrical, the workpieces produced in centre-based tests must be dismantled and discarded, adding further material costs without generating any marketable output.

Assessment in the enterprise where training takes place

Workplace-based assessment avoids many of these cost barriers and reflects real working conditions. It is, however, often rejected due to concerns about impartiality, especially if the master craftsperson who trained the apprentice also evaluates them. Systems can mitigate this challenge by deploying external assessors – for instance through trade associations that organise reciprocal assessment arrangements, where master craftspersons examine apprentices trained in other workshops.

7.2 Selected assessment and evaluation approaches

In the following, a number of common approaches to assessing and evaluating competences in the context of apprenticeships are presented.

7.2.1 Trade tests

Trade tests are among the oldest formalised assessment mechanisms used in vocational training systems in several African countries, particularly those influenced by British colonial traditions. Introduced in some contexts as early as the 1960s, they were initially developed to meet the needs of the formal economy, including public-sector employers and large-scale infrastructure projects. Over time, however, trade tests have also been used as a mechanism to assess occupation-specific practical skills of workers who acquired their competencies outside formal training pathways, being an early form of recognition of prior learning (RPL; see below) like in Ghana, Kenya, Uganda or Tanzania. The presence and role of trade tests vary considerably across countries, and they are largely absent from Francophone apprenticeship systems.

Design considerations for trade tests

When designing or reforming trade tests, several practical aspects require careful attention:

▶ Clarity and realism of test tasks

Tasks must reflect real workplace practices and typical workshop conditions. Overly complex or equipment-intensive tasks reduce fairness and feasibility.

▶ Balancing practical and theoretical components

While trade tests traditionally focused on hands-on performance, many systems later added theoretical elements to support permeability into further education. This helps progression but risks excluding candidates with limited schooling – undermining the original aim of accessibility. A balance must therefore be struck (see also the box on “Balancing theory and practice” in section 7.1).

▶ Cost and logistical barriers

Centralised testing centres can improve standardisation but often impose high indirect costs (travel, accommodation, materials). Measures to reduce these burdens are essential if tests are to remain inclusive.

▶ Consistency and assessor preparation

Clear performance criteria can support objectivity, but trade tests still depend on expert judgement. Assessors must therefore be well prepared, with strong occupational experience and shared understanding of standards.

▶ Maintaining relevance over time

As technologies and work practices evolve, test tasks must be periodically updated – ideally through structured collaboration with artisans, industry bodies and training institutions.

▶ Ghana

Long-standing trade test system balancing inclusiveness and reform pressure

Ghana has one of the longest-standing trade test systems in the region, traditionally offering accessible pathways for both apprentices and informally trained workers to gain recognition. The tests remain strongly practice-oriented at the lower levels, enabling candidates with limited formal education to demonstrate their abilities. However, as the country has expanded opportunities for progression into formal VET and higher-level qualifications, pressure has increased to incorporate more theory into the examinations. Stakeholders note that this shift strengthens upward mobility but risks reintroducing educational barriers that many informal sector workers cannot meet. Current reform efforts therefore focus on modernising test content while preserving practical accessibility – illustrating the delicate balance required to keep trade tests both credible and inclusive.

7.2.2 Module-based assessment

In apprenticeship reforms influenced by competence-based training models, some systems like Tanzania or Uganda adopt module-based assessment, in which competences are evaluated progressively rather than through a single end-of-training examination. This approach aligns well with competency frameworks that break occupations into discrete learning units.

Potential advantages

Module-based assessment offers several benefits:

- ▶ It provides regular feedback, enabling apprentices to identify learning gaps early and supporting timely remediation.
- ▶ It strengthens the link between training delivery and assessment, as modules correspond directly to specific competences.
- ▶ It can enhance transparency for learners, trainers and employers by making expectations explicit and progress visible.

Risks and limitations

Despite these strengths, a modular approach comes with notable challenges:

- ▶ It may shift attention away from the overall occupational profile, placing greater weight on isolated competences than on integrated, holistic performance.
- ▶ Because modules generally follow a predefined sequence, workplace training loses flexibility. Enterprises may struggle to align real production cycles with the mandated order of modules or to cover all components of the occupational profile.
- ▶ If assessment is to be credible, module-based assessment is significantly more demanding and costly, not least because assessment personnel need to be involved repeatedly for each apprentice.
- ▶ For these reasons, modular assessment tends to be more feasible in highly formalised apprenticeships, particularly where substantial off-the-job training exists and schools or training centres can ensure structured delivery.

Tanzania

Module-based assessment in a strongly coordinated apprenticeship model

At the National College of Tourism in Tanzania, apprenticeships use a module-based assessment approach that aligns tightly with competence-based curricula. Apprentices complete specific learning units at the college, and hotels are asked to provide corresponding workplace experiences during the same period. This sequencing allows theory and practice to reinforce one another and gives apprentices regular feedback on their progress. Because the college closely coordinates delivery, monitors workplace learning and guides enterprises, the system operates smoothly despite the structured order of modules. Hotels have embraced the model, as it clarifies expectations, supports consistent skill development and simplifies supervision. The experience shows that modular assessment can function well where strong institutional coordination exists and enterprises value the clarity and support provided by the training institution.

7.2.3 Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL)

RPL mechanisms allow individuals who have not followed a structured training pathway to have their competences recognised. While not fundamentally different in spirit from some trade test practices (see above), the RPL approach has inspired more diverse and flexible evaluation tools. It is particularly relevant in contexts where large proportions of the workforce have gained skills informally. R208 defines it as a process, undertaken by qualified personnel, of identifying, documenting, assessing and certifying a person's competencies, acquired through formal, non-formal or informal learning, based on established qualification standards.

Forms of RPL

Depending on the intended outcome, RPL can take different shapes:

▶ **Recognition leading to a qualification that is not specific to RPL**

In this model, RPL provides access to an existing qualification that can also be obtained through other pathways, such as school-based or dual VET programmes. These qualifications may be formally recognised by the state, but they can also be non-formal credentials awarded by business associations or private training providers. The key feature is that RPL serves as an alternative entry route to an established qualification rather than creating a separate certification track.

▶ **Recognition leading to a qualification or certificate specific to RPL**

In some cases, RPL schemes lead to a certificate that can only be obtained through RPL. This approach is often chosen where existing vocational qualifications are difficult to access for experienced workers from the informal economy – for example because of high theoretical requirements or formal schooling prerequisites. It may also reflect situations where the status of existing qualifications is strongly protected by particular stakeholders.

▶ **Informal recognition**

Finally, some schemes do not lead to a formal qualification at all. Instead, they provide informal recognition of competences, often independently of occupational profiles, for example through skills passports or competence attestations that document practical abilities without conferring a full certificate. They can also facilitate access to apprenticeships when prior learning is recognized to meet formal admission requirements, or shorten apprenticeship durations.

Considerations for apprenticeship design

▶ Making RPL attractive for candidates

RPL is attractive to potential candidates – such as workers or master craftspersons from the informal economy – only if the effort involved yields tangible benefits. Gaining access to a vocational qualification that enjoys little recognition in the labour market is rarely sufficient motivation. RPL becomes more compelling when it leads to credentials associated with concrete advantages, such as access to public procurement, eligibility for subsidised upskilling programmes, or improved labour-market opportunities. For this reason, RPL schemes should, wherever possible, facilitate access to existing qualifications that are valued beyond the RPL context, rather than creating certificates that remain specific to RPL alone. At the same time, care must be taken to ensure that flexible RPL arrangements do not undermine the credibility and signalling value of established qualifications.

Assessment methods within RPL

RPL mechanisms vary widely in how they evaluate competences:

- ▶ Practical skills assessments, often similar to or having evolved from trade tests, remain the most common and accessible approach, particularly where literacy levels are low and assessment must remain efficient.
- ▶ Sequential or modular assessments, allowing candidates to demonstrate competences in smaller units and accumulate evidence over time.
- ▶ Alternative evaluation tools such as portfolios, self-documentation or interviews. While valuable for capturing broader competence, these approaches generally require higher levels of literacy and may be less feasible for many informal-economy workers.

Role in the professionalisation of trainers

RPL is increasingly used to certify experienced artisans and master craftspersons who wish to participate in more formalised apprenticeship schemes. It allows them to demonstrate their competence without enrolling in lengthy training programmes, thereby strengthening the credibility of apprenticeship systems while respecting the realities of informal learning.

▶ Côte d'Ivoire

Validation of Prior Learning (VAE) as a route to the CQP for master craftspersons

Côte d'Ivoire has established a structured Validation des acquis de l'expérience (VAE) system that enables experienced practitioners in the informal economy to obtain the Certificat de qualification professionnelle (CQP) without having followed a formal training pathway. Any professional who can demonstrate relevant competences may apply, independent of age or educational background. Candidates assemble a portfolio of evidence with the support of accredited VAE advisers, documenting tasks performed, examples of work, and proof of completed contracts. Final assessment is strictly practical and conducted in authorised centres by mixed panels of professionals, trainers and apprenticeship officers.

8. Conclusions

Effective apprenticeship design in African countries inspired by ILO's Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208) offers significant opportunities to improve skills development, labour-market relevance and social inclusion across African contexts. Apprenticeships are key levers to strengthen national education and training systems by intensifying partnerships with enterprises in both formal and informal economies. At the same time, the country examples presented in this report have shown clearly that transitions to formality for apprenticeships are neither a simple nor a linear process. Apprenticeship systems are deeply embedded in local economic structures, social norms and institutional arrangements. Strengthening them therefore requires careful design choices, sustained social dialogue and a willingness to adapt policy ambitions to contextual realities.

One central insight emerging from this Guidance Note is that apprenticeships can be strengthened through different, complementary pathways. At national level, apprenticeship reform requires coherent governance arrangements that balance promotion and protection. From a policy perspective, this includes establishing or strengthening platforms for social dialogue on apprenticeship oversight, in line with the principles of the ILO Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation (No. 208). Such dialogue is essential to clarify roles and responsibilities, build trust among stakeholders and ensure that reforms are anchored in shared objectives rather than imposed through regulation alone. At the same time, labour law and other legal provisions related to apprenticeships need to be designed in ways that are inclusive and realistically enforceable, including in contexts where large parts of apprenticeship training take place in the informal economy.

From an education policy perspective, the integration of apprenticeship programmes into national education and training systems is equally important. Where apprenticeships are linked to recognised qualifications and embedded within qualifications systems or frameworks, they can support permeability, social recognition and longer-term learning pathways. However, this does not imply that all apprenticeship programmes must lead to highly formal or academic qualifications. Rather, apprenticeships should be recognised as one training pathway among others through which valued vocational qualifications can be attained without being treated as a separate or marginal track. The challenge for policy-makers lies in enabling progression without undermining the strong work orientation that defines apprenticeships and makes them attractive to employers and learners.

At the level of programme design, this report has emphasised the importance of focusing on what is feasible and sustainable in specific contexts. There are no blueprint solutions or toolkits that can simply be replicated across countries or sectors. Instead, apprenticeship programmes must be designed through careful consideration of multiple dimensions – formalization, apprenticeship relationship, education and training systems – and the trade-offs associated with different design options. To start the reform process, sectors where the gradual formalisation of apprenticeships generates tangible benefits for both learners and enterprises, for example by addressing skills shortages, improving productivity or enhancing product quality, are particularly promising.

Effective training design ultimately depends on well-defined occupational profiles and curricula, quality workplace learning, purposeful off-the-job components, and credible assessment and recognition mechanisms. Each of these elements needs to be designed in close connection with enterprise realities, labour market demand and the institutional capacities available in specific contexts. Overly prescriptive curricula, unrealistic quality standards or assessment systems detached from workplace practice risk undermining participation and sustainability, particularly

in informal economies. Conversely, well-balanced arrangements – developed through social dialogue and grounded in production logics – can enhance transparency, learning outcomes and the social recognition of apprenticeship qualifications without sacrificing flexibility. When these elements reinforce one another, apprenticeships can progressively move towards higher quality while remaining inclusive, economically viable and responsive to evolving skills needs.

Another recurring theme throughout the report is the need to acknowledge and incorporate the economic interests of enterprises. Even where apprenticeship reforms are driven primarily by social policy objectives – such as inclusion of vulnerable groups, gender equality or youth employment – sustainable implementation depends on whether enterprises perceive the arrangements as viable and attractive. This is especially true in informal labour markets, where enterprises operate under tight margins and limited regulatory oversight. Apprenticeship models that rely on short-term project subsidies may generate impressive results in pilot phases, but they are unlikely to endure once external support ends. Greater emphasis should therefore be placed on incremental reforms that can be maintained over time with realistic levels of public and private investment.

While apprenticeships need to be in the interest of employers to invest time and training resources, they also need to be attractive for learners. Only when young people’s aspirations and interests are taken seriously, and learning conditions are conducive and decent, will they be motivated to join and devote their time and effort. After graduation, they can then join the workforce as recognized skilled and productive members of society or continue on with further learning.

Monitoring, evaluation and learning play a critical role in this context. Effective apprenticeship systems require feedback mechanisms that go beyond counting enrolments or certifications. Monitoring should focus on whether apprenticeships actually deliver meaningful outcomes, whether costs and benefits are distributed in ways that stakeholders consider fair, and whether programmes remain relevant to evolving labour-market needs. Importantly, monitoring and evaluation should be embedded within ongoing social dialogue processes, enabling decision-makers to adjust design choices, address unintended effects and recalibrate objectives over time.

Finally, this Guidance Note underscores that apprenticeship reform is ultimately a balancing act. Policy-makers must navigate tensions between flexibility and standardisation, inclusion and quality, promotion and protection, and economic and social objectives. The Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation provides a valuable normative framework for this task, but its principles can only generate impact when translated into context-sensitive design choices. Progress towards quality apprenticeships is therefore best understood not as the implementation of a fixed model, but as a step-by-step process of negotiation, learning and adaptation – grounded in local realities and sustained by shared responsibility among all stakeholders involved.

Background literature

- Adams, A. V. (2008). Skills development in the informal sector of Sub-Saharan Africa. Washington DC: World Bank.
- Adams, A. V., Johansson De Silva, S., & Razmara, S. (2013). Improving Skills Development in the Informal Sector: Strategies for Sub-Saharan Africa. Washington DC: World Bank.
- Akoojee, S., & Werquin, P. (2025). A Think Piece for Apprenticeship Development in Africa and the Promotion of Better Linkages. Between Formal and Informal Apprenticeship Systems. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Anokye, P. A., & Afrane, S. K. (2014). Apprenticeship Training System In Ghana : Processes, Institutional Dynamics and Challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(7): 130-141.
- Arias, O., Evans, D. K., & Santos, I. (2019). The skills balancing act in Sub-Saharan Africa: Investing in skills for productivity, inclusivity, and adaptability. Paris – Washington DC: Agence française de développement & World Bank.
- Armah, S. K. (2021). Formal versus Informal Skills Training in Ghana. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 6(8): 585-594.
- Avenyo, E. K. (2021). Learning for product innovation in Ghana (MPRA Paper, No. 108839). Munich: University of Munich.
- Bankolé, A. R. (2021). Appropriating of dual apprenticeship in Benin: An empirical analysis in the (in)formal sector (thèse de doctorat). Parakou: Université de Parakou.
- Brück, L., & Krichewsky-Wegener, L. (2023). Learning and working with smartphones in the informal sector: New findings and recommendations for action on digitalisation in apprenticeships in sub-Saharan Africa. Eschborn: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit.
- Carton, M., & Hofmann, C. (Eds.). (2023). The education-training-work continuums: Pathways to socio-professional inclusion for youth and adults (NORRAG Special Issue, No. 8). Geneva: NORRAG & ILO.
- Chort, I., De Vreyer, P., & Marazyan, K. (2015). L'apprentissage au Sénégal, déterminants et trajectoires. *Autrepart*, 71(3): 175-193.
- Comyn, P., & Brewer, L. (2018). Does work-based learning facilitate transitions to decent work? (Employment Working Paper, No. 242). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Crépon, B., & Premand, P. (2018). Creating New Positions? Direct and Indirect Effects of a Subsidized Apprenticeship Program. Washington DC: World Bank.
- Diop, B. (2022). Appui à la Réforme de la Formation Professionnelle au Sénégal (RéFoP) : Une offre de formation pour les jeunes en adéquation avec le marché du travail. Dakar: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit.
- Filmer, D., & Fox, L. (2014). L'emploi des jeunes en Afrique subsaharienne. Paris – Washington DC: Agence française de développement & World Bank.
- Gaye, A. (2019). Entre éducation non formelle et informelle, l'apprentissage professionnel « traditionnel » au Sénégal : Analyse des pratiques des maîtres d'apprentissage et de leurs impacts sur les apprentis (thèse de doctorat). Lille: Université de Lille.

- Gewer, A. (2021). Formal and Informal VET in Sub-Saharan Africa: Overview, perspectives and the role of Dual VET. Zurich: Donor Committee for Dual Vocational Education and Training.
- Haan, H. C., & Serrière, N. (2002). Training for work in the informal sector: Fresh evidence from West and Central Africa. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Hardy, M., Mbiti, I., McCasland, J., & Salcher, I. (2019). The Apprenticeship-to-Work Transition : Experimental Evidence from Ghana. Washington DC: World Bank.
- Hardy, M., McCasland, J., & Ravallion, M. (2017). Returns to apprenticeship training in Ghana. New Haven: Innovations for Poverty Action.
- Hofmann, C., Zelenka, M., Savadogo, B., & Okolo, W. L. A. (2022). How to strengthen informal apprenticeship systems for a better future of work? Lessons learned from comparative analysis of country cases (ILO Working Paper, No. 49). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- International Labour Organization (2011). Skills for employment policy brief — Upgrading informal apprenticeship systems (Policy brief). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2012). Upgrading informal apprenticeship: A resource guide for Africa. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2013). Guide méthodologique d'encadrement des apprentis à l'usage des maîtres formateurs. Projet CEJEDRAO – Renforcement des compétences pour l'emploi des jeunes et le développement rural en Afrique de l'Ouest. Cotonou: Bureau International du Travail.
- ___ (2018). Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) Learning Package. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2020). Competency-Based Training (CBT): An Introductory Manual for Practitioners. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2020). ILO Toolkit for Quality Apprenticeships: Volume 2: Guide for Practitioners — For developing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating apprenticeship programmes. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2020). Study on quality apprenticeships in five countries of West Africa: Benin, Côte d'Ivoire, Mali, Niger and Togo. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2020). World Employment and Social Outlook Trends 2020. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2021). Case Study: The role of apprenticeships in the informal economy for skills development in Tanzania. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2021). Diagnosis on informality in targeted intervention areas of the PROSPECTS programme in Uganda. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2022). Apprenticeships Development for Universal Lifelong Learning and Training (ADULT): Towards lifelong learning and skills for the future of work – Global lessons from innovative apprenticeships. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2022). Upgrading informal apprenticeships in Jordan's car garages: A vehicle for job quality improvements and productivity gains in micro and small businesses. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2023). Statistical Brief: Apprentices in countries with large informal economies. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2023). Strengthening apprenticeship systems in the informal economy in Africa to promote quality, innovation and transitions to formality. Report on a workshop held in Cotonou, Benin, on 22-23 February 2023. Geneva: International Labour Organization.

- ___ (2024a). Quality Apprenticeships Recommendation, 2023 (No. 208). Guide for Policymakers. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2024b). Strengthening apprenticeships for transitions to formality (Policy brief). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2024c). Recommendation No. 208 on Quality Apprenticeships: What Role for Trade Unions? (Policy brief). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2025). Digitalisation and blending of training programmes. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- ___ (2026). Training package for in-house apprenticeship trainers. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- International Labour Organization, Agence Française de Développement, World Bank, & Swiss Development and Cooperation Agency (2023). Strengthening apprenticeship systems in the informal economy in Africa to promote quality, innovation and transitions to formality: Concept note for a workshop held in Cotonou, Benin, on 22-23 February 2023. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Kamara, D. S. (2022). Stratégie d'Apprentissage sans le secteur informel des métiers à Katiola en Côte d'Ivoire : Les expériences d'apprentis charpentier, maçon et couturier non-scolarisés (thèse de doctorat). Bouaké: Université Alassane Ouattara.
- Kintu, D., & Aheisibwe, I. (2019). Exploring the Effectiveness of Informal Apprenticeship in a Community of Practice: A Case Study of Katwe, Kampala-Uganda. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 8(1): 238-253.
- Lauwerier, T., Brüning, M., & Akkari, A. (2013). La qualité de l'éducation de base au Bénin : La voix des acteurs locaux. *Recherches en éducation*, 15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/ree.7368>.
- Ministère de la Formation Professionnelle (2025). Lettre de Politique sectorielle de Développement (LPSD) 2025 – 2029. Dakar: Ministère de la Formation Professionnelle.
- Ministère de la Formation Professionnelle de l'Apprentissage et de l'Artisanat (2014). Guide méthodologique d'élaboration de programmes selon l'Approche par les Compétences. Dakar: Ministère de la Formation Professionnelle de l'Apprentissage et de l'Artisanat.
- Monk, C., Sandefur, J., & Teal F. (2008). Does Doing an Apprenticeship Pay Off? Evidence from Ghana (CSAE WPS, No. 08). Oxford: Centre for the Study of African Economies.
- Nübler, I., Hofmann, C., & Greiner, C. (2009). Understanding informal apprenticeship – Findings from empirical research in Tanzania (Employment Working Paper, No. 32). Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Nunyonameh, C., Obinnim, E., & Adzivor, E. K. (2024). Apprenticeship Reforms in West Africa: An Outcome-Process Evaluation of a Pilot Dual Training Model-Based Apprenticeship Reform Scheme in Ghana. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 11(2): 223-249.
- Odjo, Z. C. (2024). Exploring the Dual Apprenticeship Programme in Benin Republic : Analyzing Opportunities and Overcoming Challenges. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4898162>
- Okwuowulu, O. (2022). Igbo apprenticeship system: A panacea for small and medium scale enterprise development. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 8(1): 41-51.
- Poortman, C. L., Illeris, K., & Nieuwenhuis, L. (2011). Apprenticeship: From learning theory to practice. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 63(3): 267-287.
- Savadogo, B. (2021). Case study: Update on improving apprenticeship in the informal economy in Benin. Geneva: International Labour Organization.

- Schraven, B., Hinz, A., Renaud, P., Rumke, C., Schommers, A., & Sikorski, A. (2013). Youth poverty in Accra: Managing urban livelihoods in informal apprenticeships. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Tamakloe, D. D. A. (2025). Reforming technical and vocational education in Côte d'Ivoire: Reimagining opportunities for the youth. Accra: African Center for Economic Transformation.
- Torm, N. (2014). Training Returns Among Informal Workers: Evidence from Urban Sites in Kenya and Tanzania. *European Journal of Development Research*, 36: 1593-1615.
- UNESCO-UNEVOC (2015). World TVET Database Senegal. Bonn: UNESCO.
- United Republic of Tanzania (2017). National Apprenticeship Guidelines. Preparing skilled young Tanzanians for today and tomorrow's Labour Market. Dodoma: Prime Minister's Office of The United Republic of Tanzania.
- Vocational Education and Training Authority (2022). Guidelines for Recognition of Prior Learning Assessment (RPLA) in Tanzania. Dar Es Salaam: Vocational Education and Training Authority.
- Walther, R. (2008). Towards a renewal of apprenticeship in West Africa: Enhancing the professional integration of young people. Paris: Agence Française de Développement.
- World Bank (1994). Labor force training support project: Memorandum and recommendation of the President of the International Development Association to the Executive Directors on a proposed credit to the Republic of Côte d'Ivoire. Washington DC: World Bank.
- . (2019). Implementation Completion and Results Report: Benin Youth Employment Project. Washington DC: World Bank.
- . (2023). Implementation Completion and Results Report: Skills Development Project. Washington DC: World Bank.
- YIEDIE (2020). Supporting Youth Employment through the Apprenticeship Model: Outcomes and Lessons from Ghana. Toronto: Mastercard Foundation.

International
Labour
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Designing apprenticeships
A guidance note for practitioners
and policy-makers in Africa

International Labour Office
4 Route des Morillons
Geneva 22, CH-1211
Switzerland

